

D1.6 Report on Methods and Practices for Science-Policy Interfaces in Support of National and Regional Soil Mission Activities Including in Living Labs

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Executive Summary

The Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” aims to establish 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. As part of the Mission Implementation Plan, clear criteria have been established to define the necessary aims, activities, participants, and context such Living Labs and Lighthouses need to align to in the context of the Mission Soil. Soil health improvement in Europe demands urgent action to address the complex challenges that spread across multiple dimensions to provide the soil ecosystem services.

More than 60% of the European soils are considered in poor health status that are affecting the soil ecosystem services and subsequently influencing the societal challenges. The soil health improvements and soil needs’ demand innovations across different levels, which transcends the specific soil management and should be seen in a value chain or systems perspective. Case studies of regional soil needs demonstrated – in a DPSIR approach – that improved and targeted policies could be an important element in changing the soil management. Thus, from the systems perspective the ability and motivation for policy makers to install supportive measures could be a key leverage point for change if they are evidence based, and this requires sound science – policy interfaces in the soil health living labs. Researchers need to co-produce and co-create knowledge with various actors and drive the innovations to address challenges in the real context. The science policy interfaces in the agri-food and environmental governance have been emerging as innovation tools to enhance the knowledge transfer and lessons into the policy process.

This deliverable addressed the knowledge gap on how wider science policy society interfaces may operate together and within the SHLL based on – among others - the literature analysis and co-designing workshops with partners. A functional definition of the SPSI is developed to match the soil health governance. A wide range of the activities implemented in the SPSIs are categorised into four functions—Stakeholder platform, Knowledge Co-creation, Knowledge Management and Knowledge Brokering. Owing to the developments in the demands of the evidence-based policy in addressing the societal demands, the theories applied in the SPSI have evolved to include range of research methods. In parallel, the principles are developed for the establishment and operationalisation of the SPSI processes. These principles, research methods, activities implemented in the SPSIs guide the designing of the future SPSIs. These tools and methods developed as the guidelines to establish the effective translation of the evidence and knowledge into actions on the policy on side and on the society on the other side (Figure 1).

The co-designing workshops identified several challenges in SHLLs and SPSI frameworks that bridge gaps between science, policy, and societal engagement. A prominent theme is the necessity of long-term engagement to ensure the successful implementation of science-policy collaborations within SHLLs. Challenges such as balancing scientific credibility with societal relevance and managing transparency, accountability, and trust are critical for fostering sustained partnerships. These challenges are compounded by institutional and bureaucratic barriers, which often introduce uncertainty into the process. Furthermore, stakeholder expectations and power dynamics must be managed effectively to maintain equitable participation and prevent imbalances in decision-making authority. These dynamics underscore the importance of inclusive and adaptive governance mechanisms that can respond to evolving needs over time.

The SPSI and SHLLs share commitment to collaborative evidence generation, capacity building and knowledge brokering. The synergetic relationship underscores the mutual reinforcement between SPSI and SHLLs. SPSI provides the frameworks and methodologies necessary for evidence synthesis and policy translation, while SHLLs offer practical, localized insights that enrich the broader knowledge base. By integrating these two initiatives, researchers can develop solutions that are both context-specific and applicable, addressing the complex, multifaceted challenges of soil health.

Figure 1: Guide to establish and operationalise the SPSI

List of Abbreviations

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CSO	Civil Society Organisations
CRELE	Credibility, Relevance, Legitimacy, and Effectiveness
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IPBES	Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Service
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LHs	Lighthouses
LLs	Living Labs
PREPSOIL	Preparing the Ground for Healthy Soils: Building capacities for Engagement, Outreach and Knowledge
SHLHs	Soil Health Lighthouses
SHLLs	Soil Health Living Labs
SMS	Soil Mission Support
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SOLO	Soils4Europe
SPSI	Science Policy Society Interface
WP	Work Package

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1. Co-Designing Science Policy Society Interfaces in the Soil Health Living Labs

1.1. The Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”

Horizon Europe is the European Union’s (EU) framework programme for research and innovation for 2021-2027. Within the programme, five missions provide actions designed to achieve bold, inspirational, and measurable goals within a specific timeframe over five major challenges identified as the greatest of our times, including: Climate Change, Cancer, Oceans and waters, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, and Soil (<https://mission-soil-platform.ec.europa.eu>). The Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" – hereafter referred to as Mission Soil – aims to establish 100 Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) by 2030, leading the transition toward healthy soils. Recognizing the vital role of soil in sustaining life on Earth, the mission underscores its significance in supporting food systems, clean water, biodiversity, and climate resilience. It emphasizes the need to address the lack of awareness among various stakeholders, such as land managers, industries, consumers, policy makers, and society, as a key driver of soil degradation, impacting its ability to provide essential ecosystem services (Panagos, Broothaerts, et al., 2024). As for the research and innovation components of the mission, these are knowledge development, knowledge sharing and transfer, knowledge application, and knowledge harmonisation which directly support to the main objective of the Mission Soil. Furthermore, the Mission Soil has eight specific objectives:

- Reduce desertification
- Conserve soil organic carbon stocks
- Stop soil sealing and increase re-use of urban soils
- Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
- Prevent erosion
- Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity
- Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
- Improve soil literacy in society

PREPSOIL and Work Package 1

The Preparing for the "Soil Deal for Europe" Mission¹ project aims to facilitate the implementation of the Mission Soil across European regions. This involves the collaborative development and use of tools

¹ PREPSOIL. <https://prepsoil.eu/> ; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070045>

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and platforms for interaction, knowledge-sharing, and co-learning. Additionally, the project includes stocktaking and dialogue to understand how a regional assessment of soil needs, supported by standardized monitoring mechanisms, can be translated into actionable initiatives within Living Labs and exemplary projects that promote soil health.

Work Package (WP) 1, task 1.4 will co-develop improved science-policy interface methods and practices for sustainable soil management and for addressing the Soil Mission objectives at national, regional and –where relevant- European levels. Activities will include co-development of best-of-practice methods for science-policy interface and advice at the national/regional level to facilitate constructive interactions and alignment between stakeholders and public governance in support of Soil Mission objectives. Results will include guidelines for consecutive steps for science-policy interaction, needs analysis, and knowledge synthesis. The tools will be co-developed and tested in four to six of the LL Regions as identified in WP2. Pilot testing will refine the methods described for wider utilisation as part of the WP3 Web Portal. The focus on the regional level will ensure that LLs can function as bottom-up information hubs for policy information and monitoring and will respect possible needs for national level engagement of policy makers/governance. The work will take into consideration experiences from the wide Science-practice interphases planned across the other WPs from the PREPSOIL Project.

Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured to systematically present the science policy interfaces in relation to the soil health governance in Europe. The structure of each chapter is presented in the Figure 2. The research methods are presented in chapter 2, results from the analysis are discussed in the chapters from 3-6. The chapter 7 synthesised key findings and presented an approach to establish and operationalise the science policy interfaces in the soil health living labs.

Relation to other initiatives and projects

In addition to relation within the PREPSOIL project actions, this deliverable also synthesizes and incorporates findings and outcomes from prior initiatives under Mission Soil and other relevant projects, along with ongoing collaborations with sister projects closely linked to PREPSOIL. As such, this section outlines both preceding and forthcoming activities and projects that are interconnected with Deliverable (D) 4.1. This deliverable is particularly interesting for the researchers engaged in the establishment of living labs, (soil, urban, forest, agriculture, agro-ecology etc.), interested in the

science policy interface research. In addition, the policy actors will also benefit from the results of the deliverable.

Figure 2: Chapter description of the deliverable 1.6
Source: Author

1.2. Concept: The Science policy interfaces and the soil health living labs

Soil health improvement in Europe demands urgent action to address the complex challenges that spread across multiple dimensions to provide the soil ecosystem services. More than 60% of the European soils are considered in poor health status that are affecting the soil ecosystem services and subsequently influencing the societal challenges (Panagos, Broothaerts, et al., 2024). Sustainable soil management and soil ecosystem services are driven by the changes in the environmental/ biophysical, socio-economic, political and legal, technological and social innovations (Bayer et al., 2023). Case studies of regional soil needs and challenges in soil use and soil health across 20 European regions demonstrated that while technical options and stakeholder motivations for improving soil management exists widely, there are barriers to overcome (Bayer et al., 2023).

The soil health improvements and soil needs' demand innovations across different levels, which transcends the specific soil management and should be seen in a value chain or systems perspective. This is because options for enhancing soil health through improved soil use and management often depends on changes in the framework conditions for the land users and therefore encompasses

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multiple actors at different levels, interactions and activities. Case studies demonstrated – in a DPSIR approach – that improved and targeted policies could be an important element in changing the soil management. Thus, from the systems perspective the ability and motivation for policy makers to install supportive measures could be a key leverage point for change if they are evidence based, and this requires sound science – policy interfaces in the soil health living labs (Figure 3). The evidence-based policy decisions are prominent options to solve many societal challenges (Zwetsloot et al., 2021). Researchers need to co-produce and co-create knowledge with various actors and drive the innovations to address challenges in the real context (Vanino et al., 2023). The science policy (society) interfaces in the agri-food and environmental governance have been emerging as innovation tools to enhance the knowledge transfer and lessons into the policy process (Juerges & Jahn, 2020; Karcher, Cvitanovic, Putten, et al., 2022; Löbmann et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Drivers identified in the regional soil needs assessments
 Source: Bayer et al. 2023

As additional supporting mechanism, the living labs as user centric approaches are enabling the evidence-based decisions at different levels (Bhatta et al., 2024). The functions of the soil health living labs (SHLL) are in the defining stage mainly drawing experiences from other sector living labs like urban, agro-ecology, agri-food systems. The knowledge transfer, co-design and innovations in the living labs is considered as the key functions (Giulia & Ylla, 2024a). The interactions between the partners representing the four groups—industry, citizens, civil society & Users, Academia, Government and public sector—the so-called quadruple helix at the SHLL level is still in very early

stages. The soil health living labs aims of innovations, formal learning and replication; and activities such as co-creation and iteration, with all the stakeholders should ideally include activities where a more traditional science-policy interface encompasses co-creation or dialogues with the relevant stakeholders (i.e. a science policy society/stakeholder interface). However, there no clarity on how the evidence transfer is organised from the soil health living labs to policy or end users.

1.3. Aim and Objective of the Deliverables

National and EU research funding programs widely have aligned their focus with the changes in the soil health priorities. Climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies to improve the soil health in EU is increasingly getting attention (Panagos, Broothaerts, et al., 2024). Moreover, the evidence-based knowledge coming out of dedicated research programmes and projects should be adapted to innovations in practice, co-developed, tested with key stakeholders including land users and disseminated to wider groups of land users. This is the idea of Soil Mission LLs and LHs. However, as mentioned, land users may face obstacles or lack of motivation due to systems level barriers (e.g. lack of market or other incentives for changing crop rotations, use of new tilling practices, new inputs), which may be alleviated partly by policies including green support schemes (e.g. under Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) pillar 2) or local policy interventions (e.g. creating markets for soil friendly crops or cultivation practices). This begs the question of which processes may ensure that policy makers at the appropriate level (City/local, region, national) understand such options and the evidence behind proposals for supporting policies. Improved science-policy interfaces may be an important element of this, given they include processes for dialogue and – possibly – co-development with other stakeholders in the area/LL in question.

The research on the guidelines to establish and operationalise the science policy interface is not well developed, particularly for the soil health at the regional or national level (Donà, 2021). This deliverable will answer this knowledge gap on how wider science policy (society/stakeholder) interfaces may operate together and within the SHLL based on – among others - the recent literature on science policy interfaces and living labs from the series of soil mission projects and co-designing workshops with partners. Therefore, the aim of the deliverable is to develop a functional definition, activities, roles of stakeholders and governance of the science policy interfaces to achieve the soil mission objectives (Figure 4). To reach the objective a first step is to present a comprehensive review of methods and tools employed in facilitating science policy interactions, focusing on their applications, effectiveness, and implications for advancing soil governance in Europe through soil

health living labs. The strategy will identify the relevant measures to be adapted by the stakeholders, researchers in particular, while establishing the soil health living labs. These measures will act as the guidelines to establish the effective translation of the evidence and knowledge into actions on the policy on side and on the society on the other side.

Figure 4: Framework to improve soil health and governance
Source: Author

2. Research Methodology

The research methods applied in this deliverable are primarily literature based and followed by the participatory co-development approaches to enhance the research accuracy. This strategy involved four stages. The following sections describe these four stages in detail and depicted in Figure 5. Initially, a concept was developed about the deliverable based on the task description from the proposal. In the next stage, the PREPSOIL deliverables and other existing soil mission funded projects are reviewed to identify the policy knowledge gaps. It is followed by the scoping review and thematic analysis. To enhance the findings accuracy, 5 co-development workshops are organised. The stakeholder selection is benefited from the regional soil needs assessments that already interacted with the experts, policy actors, living labs. Therefore, the co-designing workshops are organised together with the experts as there is enough knowledge is collected from the soil needs assessment and other soil mission funded projects.

Figure 5: Research strategy for literature review and co-designing workshops
 Source: Author

2.1. Stage 1 Regional Soil Needs and Policy Knowledge Gaps

Initially, the ongoing work from the PREPSOIL are assessed to create a robust case for the regional policy needs and to avoid the redundancy.

- The soil needs assessment reports from 20 regions in the WP 2 (Bayer et al., 2023),
- Deliverable 2.1: Synthesis of the soil needs assessments (Bayer et al., 2023)
- Deliverable 1.5: Report from Trans-European event on soil needs assessments (Gómez Grande, 2024),
- Deliverable 4.1: Report on LL/LH taxonomy, identification and mapping feeding the online interactive atlas (Giulia & Ylla, 2024a)

- Soil literacy needs from the WP 6 (Deliverable under review)

A systematic approach was taken to review above deliverables to identify the regional level policy challenges. These assessments were designed to include the diverse stakeholders from regional to national and EU level. For example, the soil needs assessments from the WP 2 involved more than 500 stakeholders across representing research, policy, Civil Society Organisations (CSO), land users, advisors. These findings from the soil needs assessments were discussed and validated with actors from policy, academics and other soil mission projects at the European mission soil week 21-23, 2023, Madrid. Similarly, WP 6 identified the aims and activities of the soil health living labs and developed the taxonomy of SHLL in participatory manner and interacted with stakeholders from all the sectors and even with other Soil mission funded projects like NATIOONS and SOILL-start up (<https://natioons.eu/>). The WP 6 expanded the stakeholders to the advisors and land users and even CSOs. The research needs from the regional point of view have been identified and stressed the policy challenges.

2.2. Stage 2 Literature review and Systematic analysis

As a first step, the ongoing and completed projects of the Soil Mission are reviewed to stock take the knowledge and avoid the duplication. The Soil Mission Support (SMS) and Soils4Europe (SOLO) projects deliverables are reviewed with attention due to author's direct involvement in these projects. In the second step, the online database Scopus was searched with a set of key words (soil health + living labs + science policy Interfaces + Science Policy Interactions) for the period of 2010-2024 to identify the relevant publications about the science policy interfaces. Since there were not many publications were available on this topic, specifically on the soil health and living labs, grey literature in the form of reports, EU funded project deliverables, final reports were also collected as a lot of research is organised and yet to be peer reviewed. Several think tanks, research institutes and even the active science policy interface initiatives were searched to collect the relevant publications. While the peer reviewed publications focused on the theories and functions of the science policy interfaces, several reports from the think tanks published practical aspects on how to establish and implement the science policy interactions. The collected publications were then screened to avoid the duplicates and non-relevant publications. The selected publications are analysed to understand the methods applied, activities implemented, functions organised, theories applied, the key outcomes in the form of benefits, outputs and lessons learned (Figure 6). The authors employed the ChatGPT to gather the relevant information on the selected aspects. The information is then converted into excel sheets and

screened manually to make sure that the data gathered by ChatGPT is accurate. This cleaned data is then analysed, and the results are presented in the chapters 4-7.

Figure 6: Literature review and analysis approach
 Source: Author

2.3. Stage 3 Participatory co-designing workshops

To enhance the understandings of the policy knowledge needs and practical implications of the science policy interfaces at the living labs, 5 participatory workshops are designed in this task. These are presented in the Table 1. The ethical guidelines from the PREPSOIL project were implemented in these workshops. The participants’ personal information is not collected, and they were informed about the PREPSOIL project and the usability of the results in the PREPSOIL project. The online co-working tools (Mural, Mentimeter) are adapted to collect the perspectives but not the personal information about the participants. These participatory workshops served different aspects of the development of research methods and tools of the science policy interfaces at the living labs. These methods will benefit the researchers involved in setting up the soil health living labs and more importantly to consortiums interested in setting up the science policy interfaces. These participatory workshops progressively developed the research tools and methods for setting up the science policy interfaces at the living labs. Ethical guidelines are strictly followed by the authors during the workshops not to collect the personal information. All the data that we collected has been anonymised during the analysis.

2.4. Stage 4 Step-by-step guide

As a last step, the knowledge from the literature review, particularly the interfaces and living labs are combined with the participant’s perspectives. A research guide is developed for the living labs and

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researchers to allow them to establish and operationalise the science policy interactions. A pragmatic approach was followed while developing these steps with a clear understanding of the science policy interfaces and soil health living labs. Enhanced concepts for the effective science policy interface research methods and tools are proposed for the soil health governance at the living labs.

Table 1: Co-designing workshops implemented

Workshop	Stakeholders and Scale	Output
1. Presentation of results at the Session at Landscapes Conference, 18.09.2024	Research, science-policy experts, Living lab experts, policy actors, soil health governance experts	Refined framework of the science policy interfaces, identification of best-of-practice methods (Stakeholders involved, activities performed, SPI functions and limitations, Experiences from/validated with scientists, policy, living lab experts.
2. Co-designing workshop with PREPSOIL Partners, 08-10.10.2024	Researchers, partners engaged in the establishment of the Soil health living labs	Identified the challenges in knowledge generation/management and transfer to Soil Mission and Soil Policy actors. Co-designed the methods and tools to communicate with Soil Mission and Soil policy actors and end users (land user)
3. Co-designing workshop with OMKI Living lab, 10.10.2024	Farmers, land users, Policy, researcher	Identified the challenges and opportunities in the regional perspective, Living labs actors' perspective on the knowledge transfer process, and the role of soil health living labs
4. Co-designing workshop with regional policy actors from Brandenburg- 10.10.2024	Regional soil policy actors, scientist, academic	Identified the policy needs, challenges and opportunities in the knowledge transfer from the regional policy and administrative actors' point of view/
5. Validation of results at the Ghent group workshop, 05-07.11.2024	Research, science-policy experts, Living lab experts, policy	Validated the results of the updated methods and tools

Source: Author

3. Regional Soil Health Challenges and Policy Needs: Stakeholder Perspectives

Soil health is fundamental to a wide array of ecosystem services, including agricultural productivity, water quality, climate regulation, and biodiversity. However, increasing pressures from urbanization, industrial activities, and climate change have led to significant soil degradation across Europe. The Soil mission sets ambitious objectives to halt soil degradation, improve soil organic matter, enhance biodiversity, and promote sustainable soil management across various land use types. Achieving the Soil Mission's objectives requires a coordinated approach at the regional and local level that integrates rigorous scientific research with policy development. The 20 regional soil needs assessments reviewed from different land uses underscore the necessity for stronger, evidence-based policy support that can guide and enforce sustainable soil management practices (Bayer et al., 2023). Refer Figure 8 for the representative regions in Europe.

Figure 7: Stakeholder groups participated in the regional soil needs assessments

Source: (Bayer et al., 2023)

The soil health governance at the regional level depends on various factors those were identified at the soil needs assessments in PREPSOIL project (Bayer et al., 2023). These variations can be seen clearly in the differences of the focused soil mission objectives from the soil needs assessments in the (Bayer et al., 2023)

Table 2. More than 500 stakeholders representing all the soil users from the 20 representative regions co-identified these soil needs. (Refer Figure 8 for additional information). Among these challenges,

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several policy implementation and knowledge gaps were identified. These challenges are summarised in the

Table 3. This analysis outlines the policy needs, research assessment, and the role of regional-level evidence in supporting effective policy interventions. It further emphasizes the importance of stakeholder inclusion, validation processes, and improvements in soil health governance. The following section explains these challenges from the regional perspective with the examples from the regions.

Figure 8: Regions of the soil needs assessments the PREPSOIL project
 Source: (Bayer et al., 2023)

Table 2: Soil mission objectives relevance in soil needs assessment regions

Land Use Category	Region/Soil Mission Objectives	1. Reduce greenhouse gas emissions	2. Conserve and improve organic carbon stocks	3. Stop soil sealing and increase areas of urban soils	4. Reduce soil pollution and restore natural soils	5. Promote soil biodiversity	6. Improve soil access to carbon and nutrients	7. Enhance the resilience of soils	8. Improve soil literacy in society
Agriculture	A01: Cow Dairy Farming								
	A02: Sheep Agrosilvopastoral								
	A03: Irrigated Arable Farming								
	A04: Olive Farming								
	A05: Annual Cropping Central								
	A06: Vine Farming								
	A07: Annual Cropping North								
	A08: Annual Cropping South								
	A09: Organic Mixed Farming East								
	A10: Mixed Farming North								
Forestry	F01: Forest North								
	F02: Forest Peatland Northeast								
	F03: Forest Tourism Southeast								
Mixed	M01: Agroforestry in Dehesa								
	M02: Alpine Tourism								
	M03: Peatlands								
	M04: Reforestation								
Urban and Post-Industrial	U01: Post-mining								
	U02: Dense Urbanism								
	U03: Post-mining								

Source: (Bayer et al., 2023)

3.1. Agricultural Land Use Regional Policy Needs

Agricultural soils are critical for food security and rural livelihoods, but they are increasingly threatened by soil degradation due to unsustainable practices, climate change, and socio-economic pressures. The cases from Extremadura and the Dehesa system illustrate the urgent need for changes in the policies that promote sustainable soil management in agricultural areas. The participants from the regional soil need assessments highlighted the following policy needs in the agriculture land use.

- **Conservation Agriculture:** Policies should promote conservation agriculture practices such as no-till farming, crop rotation, and cover cropping. These practices help maintain soil structure, reduce erosion, and improve soil organic carbon levels. This researcher highlights the need for region-specific guidelines on conservation agriculture that can be tailored to local conditions, ensuring that policies are effective in promoting soil health.
- **Sustainable Grazing Management:** In areas like the Dehesa system, policies must incentivize sustainable grazing practices that prevent overgrazing and promote the regeneration of soil organic matter. This can include rotational grazing and the implementation of agroforestry systems.
- **Water Management:** Effective water management policies are needed to mitigate the impacts of droughts and floods, which are increasingly common due to climate change. This includes the construction of check-dams and the promotion of irrigation techniques that minimize soil degradation. Understanding the long-term effects of climate change on soil health is essential for developing policies that enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability in agricultural areas.

3.2. Urban and Post-Industrial Land use Regional Policy Needs

Urbanization poses significant threats through soil sealing, contamination, and compaction. The cases from Amsterdam highlight the need for targeted urban soil management policies that align with the Soil Mission's objectives.

- **Green Infrastructure:** Urban policies should prioritize the integration of green infrastructure, such as green roofs, permeable pavements, and urban parks, to reduce soil sealing and improve urban soil health.
- **Pollution Control:** There is a need for stricter regulations on the use of chemicals that lead to soil contamination, such as heavy metals and emerging pollutants. Policies should also promote the remediation of contaminated urban soils through techniques such as phytoremediation. This aims to provide region-specific data on urban soil contamination, helping policymakers prioritize areas for intervention and select appropriate remediation techniques.
- **Community Engagement:** Public awareness campaigns and community involvement are essential for the success of urban soil management policies. These efforts should focus on educating citizens about the importance of soil health and encouraging participation in urban greening initiatives. Research on the most effective ways to engage communities in urban soil management can inform policies that foster public participation and enhance the success of soil health initiatives.

3.3. Forest Land use Regional Policy Needs

Forests play a vital role in carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and water regulation. However, forest soils are increasingly threatened by climate change, pest infestations, and unsustainable logging practices, as seen in the Vysočina region.

- **Sustainable Forest Management:** Policies should support sustainable forest management practices that enhance soil health, such as selective logging, afforestation, and reforestation. These practices help maintain soil structure, increase soil organic carbon, and support biodiversity. Stakeholders interested to identify integrated forest management practices that can be implemented across different forest types in Europe, supporting policies that balance ecological and economic objectives.
- **Pest Management:** In regions like Vysočina, where bark beetle infestations are a major threat, policies must focus on integrated pest management strategies that minimize soil disturbance while controlling pest populations.
- **Erosion Control:** In forested areas with steep topography, policies should promote the use of erosion control measures such as contour planting, terracing, and the construction of silt fences. The focus is on identifying erosion control strategies that are both effective and

feasible in different forested regions, guiding the development of targeted soil conservation policies.

3.4. Mixed Land Use Soils Regional Policy Needs

Grasslands are important for carbon storage, water retention, and biodiversity, but they are vulnerable to degradation from overgrazing, agricultural drainage, and peatland destruction. The cases from grassland areas underscore the need for sustainable management and restoration policies.

- **Peatland Restoration:** Policies should prioritize the restoration of degraded peatlands through rewetting programs, which can help restore soil organic carbon and improve water retention. These programs should be supported by financial incentives for landowners who participate in peatland restoration efforts.
- **Sustainable Grazing:** In grassland areas, policies must promote sustainable grazing practices that prevent overgrazing and support the regeneration of soil organic matter. This includes the implementation of rotational grazing systems and the reduction of stocking densities.
- **Biodiversity Conservation:** Policies should also focus on enhancing biodiversity in grassland areas by promoting the conservation of native plant species and the protection of natural habitats.

Table 3: Research needs identified from the regional soil needs assessment

Effective Practices of Sustainable soils:

- There's a lack of a cohesive approach to address climate-induced soil issues like droughts, extreme rainfall, and soil erosion.
- Lack of comprehensive understanding of effective practices tailored to specific climate-induced and soil properties.
- Small-scale initiatives for sustainable agriculture practices are in place, but they are voluntary and fragmented.

Economic Incentives for Ecosystem Services/ Economic and Financial Barriers:

- Farmers face economic pressures to adopt intensive and super-intensive farming practices due to low product prices and high operational costs. There is also a dependency on EU subsidies, which may not be sufficient or appropriately targeted to support sustainable practices.
- Current subsidies often do not adequately reward comprehensive ecosystem services. There is a need for economic incentives that support holistic soil health measures.

Adoption of Sustainable Soil Management Practices/ Accessibility and Adoption of Precision Farming Technologies/ Technological and Practical Constraints:

- While there are advancements in farming and no-till practices, widespread adoption is hindered by the high cost and lack of access to modern technologies for many farmers.
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- Policies need to be adapted to local conditions, which requires site-specific knowledge and flexibility in policy application. This adaptation is often lacking, leading to generalized and ineffective measures. Need for more localized research on soil health solutions
 - How does soil biodiversity contribute to ecosystem services, and what are the best practices for preserving it?

Policy Coordination and Governance/ Institutional and Administrative Barriers:

- There is a need for better integration and coordination of soil health policies across different regions and sectors (agriculture, environment, urban planning). Lack of coordinated efforts leads to inefficiencies and gaps in policy implementation.
- Bureaucratic Hurdles: Complex administrative procedures and bureaucratic barriers can delay or complicate the implementation of soil health policies.
- Policy Integration: Need for better integration of soil health policies with other sectors and streamlined administrative processes
- Monitoring and Evaluation: Lack of comprehensive monitoring and evaluation systems to track and improve policy outcomes

Impacts of Intensive Farming Practices:

- What are the impacts of intensive and super-intensive farming practices on soil health and productivity?
- Lack of detailed long-term impact studies of intensive farming practices on soil health

Role of Education and Training in Soil Literacy:

- There is a need for increased education and capacity-building initiatives to enhance soil literacy among stakeholders, including farmers, policymakers, and the general public.
- There is disconnect between awareness created by monitoring programs and the urgency felt by landowners and users, resulting in slow adoption of necessary practices. Insufficient data on the effectiveness of educational interventions.

Monitoring and Evaluation Systems deficiencies for Soil Health:

- Effective soil policies require robust monitoring and evaluation systems to assess their impacts and inform adaptive management. The lack of systematic monitoring frameworks and methodologies makes it difficult to evaluate policy effectiveness and adjust strategies accordingly.

Climate Resilience and Adaptation in Soil Health Policies:

- Policies need to integrate climate resilience strategies more effectively to address the impacts of extreme weather events on soil health. This includes promoting practices that enhance soil's ability to withstand and recover from climatic stresses.

Socio-Cultural and Demographic Factors:

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- The aging population of farmers and lack of succession planning contribute to the abandonment of sustainable practices and land. Encouraging young people to participate in agriculture remains a challenge.

Source: Author compilation from regional soil needs assessments (Bayer et al., 2023)

3.5. Policy and Knowledge needs

The above-mentioned regional level challenges and needs from the soil needs assessments (Bayer, 2024) points to challenge, which may need policy initiatives as support and motivation of stakeholders. The competent authority to (decide and) establish the relevant policies may reside at national or regional level depending on national laws and constitutions and the different policy areas. This will need further analysis and dialogue, for example in the specific LLs or regions, which is beyond PREPSOILs' objectives. Similar challenges have been mentioned in various studies from the soil mission projects (SMS and SOLO). However, these projects identified knowledge gaps that are not regional specific and are very general in nature. The SMS project co-developed the knowledge gaps and policy recommendations and even the actionable steps for each of the soil mission objectives. Refer Table 4 for the detailed information on the actionable steps that are developed in the SMS project. The focus on the soil mission objectives created the needs that are a bit of general and applicable to all the land uses. Several of the suggestions are very technical in nature in-terms of the definitions, indicators, data generation and access. For example, the knowledge gaps are generalised in the format of lack of knowledge, insufficient data or definitions or indicators for measurement, lack of methods to measure, and needs from the soil management perspective. This holistic approach though very practical, created very general policy recommendations. The actionable steps focused on the EU level policy implementation, or research innovation demands. There are several research needs identified that demands further research and dedicated funding.

In another soil mission funded project SOLO, the research think-tanks for each of the soil mission objectives co-developed the knowledge needs and in the process of developing roadmaps to fulfil these knowledge needs. These knowledge gaps are summarised in the Table 4. The focus has already moved from the general knowledge gaps to more specific gaps and still very technical. It is quite evident that the emphasis is on the inclusion of broader societal actors in the knowledge generation and management. The land use type's variations, and their different needs are also highlighted in these knowledge gaps. Which was also observed very strongly in the Soil needs assessment synthesis

(Bayer, 2024). However, the knowledge gaps identified by the think tanks still show lack of definitions, methods, indicators and data.

Table 4: Knowledge gaps identified for the soil mission objectives

Knowledge Gap	Policy Recommendations	Actionable Steps
1. Reduce Land degradation and Desertification		
1. Lack of clear definitions of degradation processes and drivers (including climate change, natural and human induced), and impacts.	Develop a Binding EU Soil Protection Directive with clear definitions and standardized indicators for degradation.	Draft comprehensive legislation with standardized definitions.
		Establish an EU-wide soil health monitoring framework.
2. Insufficient data, indicators and monitoring systems to quantify soil degradation and soil health.	Invest in research to develop standardized, cost-effective soil degradation monitoring tools and indicators.	Fund research initiatives focused on remote sensing technologies and soil health indicators.
		Implement pilot projects.
3. Limited research and Need for effective prevention and restoration options.	Create detailed, scalable restoration guidelines tailored to specific degradation types, with financial support.	Develop guidelines with input from soil scientists, agronomists, and local stakeholders.
		Provide grants for restoration.
2. Conserve and Increase Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) Stocks		
1. Limited research on how various soil properties and management practices interact and affect SOC levels.	Facilitate research to link soil properties and management practices with SOC levels and disseminate findings.	Conduct field trials across different soil types.
		Publish best practice guides for farmers and land managers.
2. Lack of harmonized SOC testing and monitoring methods (remote sensing) and knowledge of SOC storage potential.	Harmonize SOC testing methods across the EU and create a centralized SOC data repository for consistent monitoring.	Convene a task force to standardize SOC testing.
		Develop a centralized database accessible to researchers and policymakers.
3. Need for viable business models and policies for SOC conservation incentives.	Introduce subsidies, carbon credits, and market incentives for practices that enhance SOC, integrated into CAP.	Develop a certification program for SOC-enhancing farms.
		Provide tax incentives for businesses that sequester carbon in soils.
3. Reduce Soil Sealing and Increase Urban Soil Reuse		
1. Lack of specific data, indicators and holistic	Convert non-binding soil sealing guidelines into binding	Set specific soil sealing reduction targets.

approaches for monitoring soil sealing and land take.	regulations with clear targets and timelines.	Monitor compliance through regular reporting and audits.
2. Need for guidance on preventing soil sealing and promoting soil reuse.	Develop and disseminate guidelines on preventing soil sealing, including best practices for soil reuse in urban planning.	Create training programs for urban planners.
		Include soil reuse strategies in urban development plans.
3. Insufficient awareness of the benefits of unsealed soils and green infrastructure.	Launch public awareness campaigns on the benefits of unsealed soils and green infrastructure to promote urban sustainability.	Partner with CSOs and community groups for outreach.
		Develop educational materials and workshops for the public.
4. Soil Pollution and Restoration		
1. Limited understanding and data on the extent, sources and impact of various soil pollutants.	Implement research programs focused on understanding the behaviour of different soil pollutants and their impacts.	Fund research on the long-term effects of pollutants on soil health.
		Develop pollutant-specific management guidelines.
2. Lack of cost-effective, harmonized methods for mapping and monitoring soil pollution.	Standardize methods for soil pollution monitoring and mapping across the EU, focusing on cost-effective technologies.	Develop a suite of monitoring tools adaptable to various pollutants.
		Train local authorities on the use of these tools.
3. Need for innovative approaches to prevent and remediate emerging contaminants and soil pollution.	Promote research and development of innovative soil remediation techniques, including bioremediation and phytoremediation.	Provide grants for R&D in innovative remediation technologies.
		Implement pilot projects to test new remediation methods.
5. Prevent Soil Erosion		
1. Limited understanding on different types of erosions, trade-offs between erosion control, ecosystem services, and climate change impacts.	Integrate erosion control measures with ecosystem service and climate adaptation strategies in policy frameworks.	Conduct research on the ecological impacts of erosion control measures.
		Develop integrated management plans.
2. Need for effective, socio-economically viable erosion prevention and restoration measures.	Develop and promote cost-effective, region-specific erosion prevention measures that consider socio-economic factors.	Support local pilot projects to test and refine erosion control methods.
		Provide subsidies for adoption of effective measures.
3. Insufficient tools and data for accurately monitoring erosion and planning erosion control measures.	Invest in developing precise tools and models for monitoring erosion and planning effective control measures.	Develop GIS-based erosion risk assessment tools.
		Train local governments in the use of these tools for land management.

6. Improve Conservation of Soil Biodiversity		
1. Insufficient data and indicators to understand of the relationship between soil structure, soil organisms, soil biodiversity and habitat quality.	Fund interdisciplinary research to study the link between soil structure and habitat quality for soil biota and crops.	Establish research collaborations between soil scientists, ecologists, and agronomists.
		Disseminate research findings through workshops and publications.
2. Need for effective methods to improve soil structure in various land use contexts.	Develop best practices for soil structure improvement tailored to different land uses, such as agriculture and forestry.	Create demonstration farms to showcase soil structure improvement techniques.
		Include soil structure guidelines in agricultural extension services.
7. Reduce the EU Global Soil Footprint		
1. Need a better definition, data and indicators, Limited understanding of the global impact of EU land use practices on soils beyond biomass, food and timber?	Conduct comprehensive assessments of the EU's global soil footprint and integrate findings into trade and environmental policies.	Commission studies on the global soil impacts of EU imports and exports.
		Publish reports and integrate findings into policy recommendations.
2. Need for strategies to reduce the negative impacts of EU land use on global soil health.	Develop strategies to minimize the EU's global soil footprint, including sustainable sourcing and land use practices.	Implement sustainable sourcing standards for EU imports.
		Encourage international cooperation on soil conservation initiatives.
8. Increase Soil Literacy		
1. Significant gap in awareness and understanding of soil health issues among the public and policymakers.	Launch a comprehensive soil literacy campaign targeting both the public and policymakers, emphasizing the importance of soil health.	Partner with educational institutions to develop soil health curricula.
		Use media campaigns to reach a broad audience.
2. Lack of targeted educational resources, definitions, tools, methods and outreach programs to raise soil literacy.	Develop targeted educational resources and outreach programs to raise awareness about soil health and sustainable management.	Create soil health modules for schools and universities.
		Organize community events focused on soil conservation education.

Source: Author Compilation

3.6. Need for Regional Evidence-Based Policy

The current legislative framework for soil protection in the European Union is characterized by fragmentation and a lack of binding commitments, which significantly limits its effectiveness in addressing the complex challenges of soil health. While several EU policies indirectly contribute to soil protection, they do not comprehensively or adequately cover all aspects of soil health and management. For instance, the CAP, which plays a significant role in shaping land use and farming practices across the EU, includes measures aimed at maintaining soil health, such as crop diversification, maintaining permanent grassland, and establishing ecological focus areas. However, these measures are often voluntary or incentivized rather than mandatory, leading to inconsistent implementation and effectiveness across member states. These policies primarily address specific issues, like water quality and agricultural practices, without a holistic approach to soil health. As a result, many aspects of soil degradation, such as contamination and loss of soil organic carbon, are inadequately covered, leading to inconsistent protection across different regions.

Moreover, other environmental directives, such as the Nitrates Directive, the Water Framework Directive, and the Habitat Directive, address specific environmental issues related to soils, such as preventing nitrate pollution, protecting water quality, and conserving natural habitats. Although these directives contribute to soil protection, they do so only tangentially and do not provide a holistic approach to soil health. For example, while the Nitrates Directive aims to prevent groundwater pollution from agricultural sources, it does not address other critical aspects of soil health, such as soil organic carbon content, soil erosion, or biodiversity. The lack of a dedicated soil protection framework has resulted in uneven soil protection efforts across the EU, with significant variations in the adoption and enforcement of soil health measures among member states. This inconsistency hinders the EU's ability to tackle soil degradation effectively and undermines the broader environmental and climate goals set forth in the European Green Deal. Furthermore, the absence of binding targets and standardized monitoring protocols means that the current policies do not provide a clear, unified direction for soil health, nor do they ensure accountability for soil degradation.

On this background, the European Commission has proposed a Soil Monitoring Law which is currently under negotiation between the European Parliament and the council of ministers (Commission, 2024). The idea is to agree on a solid and coherent monitoring framework for all soils across the EU so Member States can take measures to regenerate degraded soils. Besides the – to a certain degree – harmonized monitoring, the objectives include that Member States should define sustainable soil

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management practices suited to the national and regional contexts and define which practices should be implemented by soil managers and which should be banned because they cause soil degradation. The adoption of the Soil Monitoring Law is crucial for establishing a coherent, binding framework that can effectively address the complex challenges of soil degradation. By providing clear targets, harmonized monitoring, and comprehensive protection measures, the law would play a pivotal role in safeguarding the EU's soil resources, supporting ecosystem services, and achieving the EU's environmental and climate objectives. The urgency of implementing such a law is underscored by the need to ensure the long-term sustainability of Europe's soils, which are essential for life, prosperity, and the well-being of future generations. Thus, with the coming implementation of the Soil Monitoring Law one could assume that this would facilitate dialogues between the policy makers/civil servants, scientists and other stakeholders, which supports the ideas of using LLs as a vehicle or partner in this process.

Integration with Other Policies: To maximize its effectiveness, the Soil Monitoring Law must be integrated with existing EU policies, ensuring a holistic approach to environmental sustainability. The European Green Deal serves as a comprehensive framework under which the Soil Health Law should align with other key initiatives, such as the Biodiversity Strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the Zero Pollution Action Plan. The Biodiversity Strategy aims to halt and reverse biodiversity loss by 2030, recognizing that healthy soils are vital for supporting diverse ecosystems. The Soil Health Law can contribute to these goals by promoting practices that enhance soil biodiversity, such as reduced tillage, cover cropping, and organic farming, which also improve soil structure and function. The Farm to Fork Strategy seeks to create a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food system. Soil health is a critical component of sustainable agriculture, impacting crop yields, food quality, and ecosystem services. The Zero Pollution Action Plan focuses on reducing pollution in air, water, and soil to create a toxic-free environment. The Soil Health Law should establish stringent controls on soil pollutants, aligning with the Zero Pollution goals by reducing the levels of harmful chemicals and contaminants that affect both soil health and human well-being. By embracing flexibility and promoting cross-policy synergies, the law can effectively safeguard soil health, enhance environmental sustainability, and contribute to the EU's overarching goals for climate action, biodiversity, and human health.

4. Science Policy Society Interface: Theory and Activities

The following analysis is developed from the selected literature (112 publications) on the science policy interfaces. A systematic approach is taken to identify the activities, functions, principles, theories and methods used, benefits of the activities, challenges and recommendations. The thematic analysis is adapted to identify the trends and developments in the science policy interfaces to guide the researchers interested in both the interfaces and soil health living labs. The following chapter presents the details of the results from the analysis.

4.1. Definition of Science Policy Society Interface

The science to policy or science for policy interfaces have been developed at the national, international level and EU level. The policy makers are increasingly depending on the scientific evidence for their decisions at the international level (Donà, 2024; Singh et al., 2021) while no overview of such a possible trend at national/regional level is available. At the same time, it is increasingly discussed that scientific input is not the only source of evidence in the policy making (Spruijt et al., 2014; Turnhout, 2024; Waylen et al., 2023) and increasing role of the knowledge brokers (Cvitanovic et al., 2025). The international level interfaces like Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC), Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), Food and Agriculture Organisation have well established the process for the science-based evidence gathering and knowledge brokering (Donà, 2024; Singh et al., 2021). Some countries also established national level processes together with the national research agencies to gather evidence to support their agri-environmental policy process (Ruth Stewart & Patiño-Lugo, 2024; Welch et al., 2024). Several of these interfaces proposed different definitions suiting to their context and focused area. The following definition is developed to suit the soil health governance at the regional level.

“Institutional arrangements (organizations, living labs, initiatives or projects) and processes of science advice, which may allow for co-creation and, interdisciplinary between scientists, policy makers and if possible – other stakeholders is defined as the science policy society interface” (based on the definitions from the (Braun et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2021; Webb et al., 2022).

Figure 9: Science Policy Society Interface model

Source: (Young, 2013a, 2013b)

4.2. Theories of Science Policy Society Interfaces

Theories surrounding science for policy have significantly evolved over time, particularly from early 2000, reflecting shifts not only in the understanding of how scientific knowledge interacts with policymaking but also in how evidence is used by various stakeholders, including other end users (Cash & Belloy, 2020). This evolution has paralleled the increasing complexity of societal challenges, such as soil health, and soil ecosystem service provisions, and the need for more adaptive, inclusive, and responsive frameworks (Welch et al., 2024). This section will present a general overview of the theories used in the SPSIs.

Early Linear Models: In the early stages of SPI development, the dominant framework was the Linear Model of knowledge transfer. This model, often referred to as the "loading-dock" approach, assumed that scientific knowledge, once generated, could be simply handed off to policymakers who would then implement it as policy (Cash et al., 2003; Cash & Belloy, 2020). The underlying assumption was that more and better data would naturally lead to better policy outcomes. This model was particularly prevalent in areas such as agricultural policy, where scientific research on crop yields or pest control was directly translated into guidelines for farmers (Cammarano et al., 2023). Similarly, in forestry, evidence on sustainable practices was expected to be directly adopted by forest managers (Westwood et al., 2023). However, the limitations of this approach became apparent as it often failed to account for the complex realities of policy implementation and the diverse needs of end-users like farmers and foresters (Böcher, 2016).

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Interactive and Contextual Models: The shortcomings of the linear model drawn a shift towards more interactive and contextual frameworks. The Boundary Organization Theory emphasized the role of intermediary organizations in facilitating communication between scientists and policymakers (Andrews et al., 2024). The idea of boundary organizations – such as IPBES- not only translated scientific findings into policy-relevant terms but also considered the socio-economic contexts in which policies would be applied (Wiegleb & Bruns, 2022). This shift was particularly relevant in fields like international governance, where the needs of intentional policy needs were often at odds with the rigid outputs of scientific research (Wiegleb & Bruns, 2022). The boundary organization framework helped bridge this gap by involving national policy actors early in the research process, ensuring that the scientific evidence produced was both relevant and actionable in real-world planning scenarios (Andrews et al., 2024; Bednarek et al., 2018; Cvitanovic et al., 2024; Neal et al., 2022; Schröter et al., 2023; Sobral et al., 2024; Tellmann & Gulbrandsen, 2022; Wiegleb & Bruns, 2022). In the area of Soil management and within the framework of the Mission Soil, a hypothesis could be that LLs as multi-stakeholder organizations may undertake this role, exactly because the co-creation activities would facilitate the development of and translation of context dependent research into policy relevant knowledge (Donà, 2021; Geenhuizen, 2018; Juhola et al., 2024).

The Emergence of Knowledge Brokers: An important development in the evolution of SPSIs is the concept of Knowledge Brokers (Jagannathan et al., 2023; Juhola et al., 2024). Knowledge brokers act as intermediaries between science and policy, like boundary organizations, but with a stronger emphasis on facilitating the use of scientific knowledge across various sectors and stakeholders (Cvitanovic et al., 2025; Reinecke, 2015; Tuohy et al., 2024). These brokers play a crucial role in translating complex scientific information into language and formats that are accessible and relevant to non-scientific audiences, such as policymakers, farmers, and urban planners (Gluckman, 2018; Juhola et al., 2024). The role of knowledge brokers has become increasingly recognized as essential in contexts where scientific knowledge must be integrated into policy and practice under conditions of uncertainty and complexity (Cvitanovic et al., 2024; Dupont et al., 2024; Jagannathan et al., 2023; Karcher et al., 2023; Karcher, Cvitanovic, Putten, et al., 2022; Karcher et al., 2024; Turnhout, 2024). In the case of EU climate policy, formal structures of the brokerage sustained over informal structures during the politicisation of the climate policy (Dupont et al., 2024). In EU agri-food systems, knowledge brokers are increasingly supporting the spread of scientific research related to climate resilience and sustainable farming practices among various stakeholders (Cammarano et al., 2023; Elisabeth et al., 2022).

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Knowledge brokerage in its most simplistic description is the process of effectively transmitting the results of evidence synthesis to the policymaker or any other user (Gluckman et al., 2021; Pielke, 2007). Knowledge brokers align between the needs and/or request of the policy community/other users and the evidence synthesis provided. They are also skilled with robust methods for the evidence synthesis, transdisciplinary, with appropriate expert inputs (Cvitanovic et al., 2025; Gluckman et al., 2021; Reinecke, 2015). Creates a robust understanding of the implications and limitations of the evidence. Advice in the form of choices/options rather than making specific recommendations and minimizes the biases and values of those providing advice. And finally, does not attempt to take a role in the policy choice process.

Co-Production of Knowledge: The next major evolution in SPSI theories was the emergence of the Co-Production of Knowledge framework, which recognized that scientific knowledge is not merely applied but is actively constructed through interactions between scientists, policymakers, and other stakeholders, including farmers, foresters, and urban designers (Cvitanovic et al., 2024; Kalsnes et al., 2023; Karcher, Cvitanovic, Putten, et al., 2022; Kruijff et al., 2022; Pohl et al., 2010; Rosemartin et al., 2023; Thune et al., 2023; Turnhout et al., 2020). This approach highlighted the importance of engaging end-users in the research process, ensuring that the knowledge produced is both relevant and legitimate. For example, in the context of agriculture, co-production has led to more participatory research models where farmers are involved in the design and implementation of experiments, ensuring that the outcomes are directly applicable to their farming practices. This approach has also been employed in forestry, agri-food systems, where land use managers work alongside researchers to co-develop sustainable management practices that are tailored to specific ecological and socio-economic conditions (Jagannathan et al., 2023; Maas et al., 2022; Turnhout, 2024).

Adaptive Governance and Reflexive Approaches: As the complexity of environmental and social challenges continued to grow, theories of Adaptive Governance emerged, focusing on the need for governance systems that are flexible, learning-oriented, and capable of adapting to new information and changing conditions (Tengö et al., 2017). Adaptive governance is particularly relevant in the context of climate change, where both policymakers and stakeholders such as farmers and foresters must continuously adapt their strategies in response to evolving scientific evidence (Westwood et al., 2023). This framework has been critical in managing social-ecological systems, where the integration of scientific evidence with local practices and knowledge systems is necessary for sustainable outcomes. For example, in forestry, adaptive governance has allowed for the development of

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management practices that are responsive to both ecological changes and the needs of local communities (Cvitanovic et al., 2015).

Social Learning and Participatory Approaches: The increasing recognition of the importance of stakeholder involvement in SPSIs led to the integration of Social Learning and Participatory Approaches into SPSI theories (Dupré et al., 2021; Mason et al., 2024; Massari et al., 2023). Social learning involves the collective learning processes that occur when different stakeholders, including scientists, policymakers, and end-users like farmers and urban designers, engage in dialogue and share knowledge ((ed.), 2024; Kapoor et al., 2023; Sarkki et al., 2020; Tinch et al., 2018; Young et al., 2014; Young, 2013a, 2013b). In agriculture, social learning has been instrumental in promoting the adoption of sustainable practices, as farmers learn from each other's experiences and from the research findings presented by scientists. In urban design, participatory approaches have led to the co-creation of urban spaces that reflect the needs and values of local communities, enhancing both the relevance and legitimacy of the outcomes. Participatory approaches also address the challenges of applying scientific knowledge in diverse and complex real-world contexts. By involving stakeholders in the research process, these approaches ensure that the knowledge produced is not only scientifically robust but also socially and culturally relevant, which, ideally, should lead to more effective and sustainable policy outcomes (Kapoor et al., 2023; Kelemen et al., 2021; Sarkki et al., 2020; Simo et al., 2014).

Integration of Evidence-Based Policy Frameworks: The evolution of SPSI theories also reflects a growing emphasis on Evidence-Based Policy Frameworks, which advocate for the systematic use of scientific evidence in policy-making processes. This framework has been particularly influential in health, agriculture, and environmental policy, where the rigorous application of evidence is essential for effective decision-making (Daniel & Vicky, 2022; Juhola et al., 2024; Karcher, Cvitanovic, Putten, et al., 2022; Krieger & Melchor, 2022; Murken et al., 2024; Ruth Stewart & Patiño-Lugo, 2024). In forestry, evidence-based policies have led to the adoption of sustainable forest management practices that are grounded in scientific research, ensuring the long-term health of forest ecosystems (Westwood et al., 2023). In urban planning, evidence-based approaches have been used to design cities that are more resilient to climate change, integrating scientific insights into infrastructure development and land-use planning (Young, 2013a).

In conclusion, the evolution of theories in SPSIs reflects a broadening understanding of how scientific knowledge is created and interacts with policymaking and how evidence is used by various stakeholders (refer Table 5 for additional information). It was also observed that the benefits of the

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interfaces have been well documented. The Figure 10 summarises the key benefits of the interfaces that were collected from the literature. The benefits of the interfaces are also developed in collaboration with the developments in the theories. From early linear models to contemporary frameworks that emphasize co-production, adaptive governance, and participatory approaches, the theoretical landscape of SPSIs has become increasingly sophisticated and responsive to the needs of diverse end-users. The emergence of knowledge brokers as a key component in SPSIs highlights the need for skilled intermediaries who can effectively translate and communicate scientific knowledge, ensuring that it informs policy and practice in a meaningful way. This evolution underscores the importance of designing SPSIs that are not only scientifically robust but also socially relevant, ensuring that scientific knowledge effectively informs policy and practice in a complex and changing world.

Table 5: Theories of the Science policy society interface

Theory Description
Linear Knowledge Production: Traditional approach to knowledge production where science operates independently of societal influences, focused on basic research.
Triple Helix Model (Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff 1995): Emphasizes the dynamic interaction between Academics, industry, and government for knowledge production.
Interactive Knowledge Production (Nowotny et al. 2001): Shift from linear, disciplinary research to socially distributed, problem-oriented, and transdisciplinary research involving various societal stakeholders.
Saliency, Credibility, Legitimacy Framework (Cash et al. 2002): Evaluates scientific information used in policymaking based on its relevance, trustworthiness, and legitimacy in decision-making processes.
CRELE (Credibility, Relevance, Legitimacy, and Effectiveness) (Sarkki et al. 2014): Expands on the SCL framework by adding effectiveness to assess how scientific knowledge influences policy decisions.
Four Models of Research-Policy relations (Boswell & Smith 2017): Knowledge-driven, Problem-solving, Interactive, and Political/strategic models for understanding policy impact.
Transformative Innovation Policy (Topp et al. 2018): Focuses on systemic change in socio-technical systems through innovation policy, recognizing the need for addressing grand societal challenges
Mission-Oriented Innovation (Mazzucato 2018): Policy frameworks designed to tackle grand societal challenges through focused, outcome-oriented innovation efforts across sectors and disciplines.
Complex Systems Theory (Renn et al. 2019): Recognizes that policy problems are complex and interrelated, requiring interdisciplinary approaches and continuous adaptation.
Adaptive Governance (Renn et al. 2019): Advocates for flexible governance structures that can adapt to new scientific information and evolving societal needs.

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Post-Normal Science (Renn et al. 2019): Recognizes the complexity of science in decision-making under uncertainty, emphasizing extended peer communities and the role of societal values.

Hybrid Management (De Donà 2021): A management approach that integrates scientific, technical, and local knowledge into governance strategies.

Distributed Cognition (Cradock-Henry & Frame 2021): Focuses on how knowledge is collectively produced and shared across networks of actors, highlighting the collective cognitive process in complex policy environments.

Boundary Organizations (De Donà 2021): Examines organizations that work at the boundary of science and policy, facilitating communication, collaboration, and knowledge translation across disciplines.

Policy Networks (Oliver et al. 2022): Focuses on the network of actors (scientists, policymakers, interest groups) involved in policy development and knowledge exchange.

Knowledge Brokerage (Karaulova & Edler 2023): Concept of intermediaries or brokers who translate scientific research into actionable knowledge for policy development.

Evidence-Informed Policymaking (Pedersen 2023): Emphasizes the integration of research evidence into policy processes, advocating for structured, iterative engagement between science and policy.

Actionable Knowledge Framework (Jagannathan et al. 2023): Prioritizes the creation of knowledge that is usable and directly applicable to real-world policy challenges, emphasizing tangible outcomes.

Knowledge Mobilization (Durrant et al. 2024): Strategies aimed at ensuring that scientific knowledge is actively disseminated and utilized in policy and practice, involving systematic approaches to engagement.

Communities of Practice (Carroll & Crawford 2024): Refers to groups that share knowledge and expertise on specific areas, enhancing collaborative efforts in science-policy interfaces.

Co-Production (Schmidt et al. 2024): The collaborative creation of knowledge between scientists and policymakers, emphasizing the need for mutual learning and problem-solving.

Source: Author Compilation

Figure 10: Benefits of the Science policy society interfaces

Source: Author

4.3. Principles of the SPSIs

The SPSIs adapted principles to follow in the processes of establishment and implementation. A selected list of principles is presented in the **Error! Reference source not found.** The scientists shall observe the processes more carefully and adopt the principles as early as possible in the establishment and operationalisation of the SPSIs (Fritz & Binder, 2020; Scharfbillig et al., 2021). These principles will guide the participants with clear ideas on the roles and responsibilities. Initial principles of credibility, relevance and legitimacy have been expanded to additional principles owing to the transitions in SPSIs (Cash & Belloy, 2020; Heink et al., 2015; Project, 2014). The EU funded projects are subject to ethical guidelines and FAIR data sharing principles, and open access publication principles. In addition to these top-down principles, the researchers are encouraged to adopt the suitable principles to improve the efficiency of the interfaces. The mentioned principles is – on the one hand- an attempt to include the experiences mentioned above (sect 4.1 and 4.2) – especially the limitations of an isolated SPSI risking not understanding the practical context or being biased towards the dominant regime and framing of challenges. However, principles like inclusivity, coproduction of knowledge and adaptability may create risks – on the other hand – to compromise the integrity of and independence of the science advice provided. This dilemma has not found its clear solution in theory nor widely in practice according to our literature review.

Table 6: Principles of the Science policy society interfaces

Principle	Description
Credibility	Trustworthiness of the evidence being produced, rigorous methods and unbiased data.
Relevance	Evidence is timely, applicable and useful to policy needs & societal challenges.
Legitimacy	Fairness, inclusive, representation in the decision-making process to build trust in the outcomes.
Effectiveness	Establish robust mechanisms for the ongoing evaluation of impact and effectiveness, informed by scientific evidence.
Inclusivity	Broad representation, including marginalized voices such as Indigenous communities in decision-making.
Transparency	Open and participatory processes in decision-making, clear, accessible communication and decision-making processes.
Adaptability	Allows flexibility in SPI processes to respond to new evidence, changing conditions, and emerging challenges.
Iterative	Continues feedback loops to revise and refine the processes, ensuring learning and adaptation
Independence	Guarantees that scientific knowledge and advice remain free from external political or economic influence, maintaining objectivity.
Accountability	Imposes responsibility and ethical conduct in the use of scientific evidence for policymaking.
Pluralism	Advocates for fairness, equity, and the inclusion of diverse and marginalized voices in decision-making and knowledge production.
Reflexivity	To critically reflect on their own roles, perspectives, and assumptions in the knowledge prod, policy processes.
Trust	Build trust through transparent, continuous engagement, and respecting differing views.
Power	Being aware of and addressing the power.
Resilience	Ensures that SPSIs are resilient to political pressures, conflicts, and other external challenges, maintaining focus on long-term objectives.
Co-Production	Joint creation of knowledge involving scientific experts, policy actors and stakeholders.
Communication	Developing clear, strategic communication plans to convey scientific findings effectively to policymakers and the public.
Interdisciplinary	Integrates experts from diverse fields to address complex, cross-cutting problems.
Institutional design	Advocates for robust institutions, resilient, adaptable, and capable of facilitating long-term interactions institutional frameworks that enable effective science-policy communication and interaction.
Ethics	Ensures the protection of cultural and ethical values, especially in interactions between diverse stakeholder groups, including marginalized communities.
Capacity building	Enhances the ability of stakeholders to engage meaningfully in SPIs by providing necessary training, skills, and resources.
Empowering stakeholders	Provides stakeholders with tools and resources to actively contribute to knowledge co-production and decision-making processes.

Source: Author

4.4. Functions and Activities of SPSI

The SPSIs operates along different spatial, administrative and temporal scales. The processes may be very formal and purposively designed structures, such as IPCC, or IPBES. At EU, national and regional levels, it is common to find advisory boards or technical working groups, set up by policy actors to synthesise and feed the evidence. The functions of the interface shall be defined in the beginning stages to make sure that the science to policy interface just does not operate to communicate (mostly one way, without any purpose) scientific knowledge in the form of policy briefs and research synthesis publications. This is particularly important for the complex soil health governance involving societal interaction and bio-physical research. The regional level soil health improvements depend on the quality of evidence and mechanisms of knowledge transfer and exchange (Donà, 2024; Gómez Grande, 2024; Keesstra et al., 2024; Panagos, Borrelli, et al., 2024; Veenstra et al., 2024).

The nature of the SPSIs allows to implement a wide range of activities by adopting various methods and tools from the research and stakeholder interactions. The definition of the SPSI in the section 4.1 guided in the categorisation of the activities into four main functions—Stakeholder platform, Knowledge Co-Creation, Knowledge Synthesis, Knowledge Brokering (Table 7). These functions match with the overall objectives of the living labs that are built on stakeholder dialogue and co-creation at the local level. As a first step of the SPSI, the initiation with the agenda setting, definition of the roles and responsibilities, establish the roles and responsibilities together with the stakeholders all fall into the category of stakeholder platform. It is followed by the category of co-creation of knowledge which includes the research, generate new evidence where there are gaps and needs. The conventional research methods and tools that are implemented in the research programs are also included in this function. The knowledge management and brokering are kind of specific to the SPSI process that involves a lot of activities to manage and transfer the knowledge to end users. These functions and activities depend on the institutional arrangements, policy cycle mechanisms, national policy structures, projects, programs that implement the interfaces. The functions further describe the nature of intervention by different actors including from the policy. The knowledge brokering function creates the interaction between policy-science and society by adapting the principles those are mentioned in the section 4.3. One of the key principles will be to enable the independence of the knowledge from different actors. This includes the academics and other forms of knowledge generating actors such as think tanks, farmer groups involved in the processes. The analysis of the

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functions, activities and their corresponding benefits would guide the researcher to choose suitable methods and tools while establishing and implementing the SPSIs.

The literature review further identified the benefits linked to these various activities. These activities play a crucial role in bridging the gap between knowledge production and its application in evidence-based decisions across users. Many activities yield similar benefits as they overlap with the stakeholder interaction, co-production and application. Table 7 summarised the key benefits under each function. One of the primary benefits of these wide range of activities is their ability to bridge the gap between science and policy by fostering trust and dialogue among stakeholders (Donà, 2021; Sánchez-García et al., 2023). This trust-building process creates opportunities for inclusive and participatory approaches to decision-making, where diverse voices, including those of scientists, policymakers, and local communities, are heard and considered. This not only enhances the credibility of decisions but also contributes to more robust and adaptive policy frameworks (Heink et al., 2015; MacKillop et al., 2023; Posner et al., 2016). The dissemination of scientific knowledge is another critical benefit of SPSI activities. By translating complex research findings into accessible formats, these activities make science more understandable and actionable for policymakers and other stakeholders. This knowledge transfer not only enhances the impact of research but also empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions (Ferre et al., 2022).

By bringing together experts from various fields, the interdisciplinary activities create a space for holistic problem-solving that transcends disciplinary boundaries (Gaebel et al., 2024; Pe'er et al., 2024). This integrative approach broadens the scope of potential solutions and ensures that policies and interventions are grounded in a comprehensive understanding of the issues at hand. Furthermore, these activities play a crucial role in enhancing policy coherence and integration (Cristobal Marin Rojas, 2023). SPSI activities facilitate this integration by identifying synergies and trade-offs among various objectives, ensuring that policies are aligned and mutually reinforcing. The participatory activities enhance the legitimacy of decision-making processes by promoting transparency and accountability principles. By involving diverse stakeholders in discussions and deliberations, the activities create a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for outcomes. This inclusivity is particularly important in addressing contested issues, where divergent interests and perspectives can lead to conflicts. Stakeholder based activities help mediate these differences by facilitating open dialogue and negotiation, thereby fostering consensus and reducing resistance to policy implementation (Gaebel et al., 2024; Kalsnes et al., 2023; Strauss et al., 2023; Velden et al., 2024). By engaging various actors in collaborative processes, the capacity building activities enhance the skills

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and knowledge of participants, empowering them to navigate complex systems and address multi-faceted challenges effectively (Jolibert & Wesselink, 2012; Singletary et al., 2022). Moreover, the participatory nature of activities encourages mutual learning, where stakeholders share experiences, co-create solutions, and develop a shared understanding of problems and their potential resolutions. By providing a platform for their voices to be heard, these activities ensure that policies are more equitable and responsive to the needs of all stakeholders. By bringing together diverse stakeholders, these activities build networks and partnerships that enhance the collective capacity to address complex challenges (Juhola et al., 2024; Kelemen et al., 2021; Pirrone et al., 2022). This collaborative approach not only strengthens individual and institutional capacities but also creates a foundation for long-term sustainability and resilience.

Another significant benefit of research activities is their contribution to innovation and experimentation. By creating spaces for piloting new ideas and approaches, these activities enable stakeholders to test and refine solutions before scaling them up (Calafat, 2024; Wilke & Pyka, 2024). This experimental approach is particularly valuable in dynamic and uncertain contexts, where traditional methods may no longer be effective. For instance, living labs will create these spaces to provide valuable insights into adaptive management strategies, helping stakeholders respond more effectively to changing environmental and socio-economic conditions (Compagnucci et al., 2021; Gardezi et al., 2024; Potters et al., 2022). The collaborative and evidence-based activities also contribute to long-term sustainability by fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptation. By monitoring and evaluating the outcomes of policies and interventions, these activities provide valuable feedback that can inform future decisions. This iterative process ensures that policies remain relevant and effective in the face of emerging challenges and uncertainties. Moreover, the emphasis on learning and adaptation encourages a proactive approach to problem-solving, where stakeholders anticipate and address potential issues before they escalate.

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Table 7: Activities with Corresponding Benefits of the SPSI Functions

Source: Author Compilation

4.5. Lessons and outlook of SPSI

An important step in the SPSI implementation is the identification of challenges to improve the SPSI processes. Several challenges are identified in establishment and implementation of the SPSIs and summarised in Table 8. The main challenge linked with SPSIs is lack of resources for establishing and implementing active stakeholder engagement, evidence synthesis and exchange. The conditions such as changes in personal, institutional arrangements, short term project cycles create additional uncertainty in the process. The regional variations, lack of understanding of the local context reduces trust in the process and that directly affects the quality of the evidence from the SPSIs. The standard problems of complex bureaucracy, regulations that limit the experimental space etc., could be avoided with a strong emphasis on the CRELE principles. The young academics, researchers and alike also require dedicated capacity building programs on the SPSIs. When interacting with diverse actors from the policy to end users, the researchers’ interpersonal skills play essential role in the establishing trust. Understanding of the local cultural beliefs, knowledge on the policy cycle and broader programs is essential for the researchers to overcome these challenges.

Table 8: Challenges in the SPSI implementation

Challenges	Lack of Resources	Uncertainty
Issue and context	Expertise/capacity	Changes in personnel
Bureaucracy	Funds	Changes in the political/managerial structure (interlocutors, priorities)
Complex regulatory context	Interest	Differences of context at local level
Different interests and perspectives	Knowledge	Disparities among EU countries
Evaluations and monitoring by policymakers	Suitable finance and business models	
System not adequately structured	Time/short term perspective	
The cultural beliefs	Trust	
Sensitive to various biases and interests	composition of advisers and the quality of the dialogue between advisers and policymakers	

Source: Author

Enhancing SPSI processes requires an integrated approach that addresses structural, procedural, and relational aspects to ensure they are more effective, inclusive, and adaptive to emerging challenges (Karcher, Cvitanovic, Putten, et al., 2022; Karcher, Cvitanovic, Shellock, et al., 2022). One of the most frequently cited areas for improvement is the need for better integration of diverse forms of knowledge. SPSI activities often privilege scientific and technical expertise while undervaluing local, traditional, and indigenous knowledge systems. This imbalance limits the comprehensiveness of

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solutions and may alienate key stakeholders. To address this, SPSIs must create frameworks and adapt the principles that genuinely value and incorporate pluralistic knowledge. This could involve establishing mechanisms to facilitate mutual learning between scientists, policymakers, and local communities, as well as providing platforms for the co-production of knowledge. Recognizing diverse perspectives not only enriches the knowledge base but also increases the legitimacy of decisions and fosters trust among participants.

The analysis also highlights the need for greater stakeholder engagement throughout SPSI processes. Although many activities are designed to be participatory, in practice, certain groups, such as marginalized communities, smallholder farmers, and CSOs operate at regional level, are often excluded or inadequately represented. To improve inclusivity, SPSIs should adopt more robust engagement strategies that prioritize underrepresented voices and actively seek their input. Early and sustained stakeholder involvement ensures that diverse perspectives shape decision-making, enhancing both the relevance and acceptance of outcomes.

However, as mentioned, principles re. Inclusivity, coproduction of knowledge may create risks to compromise the integrity of and independence of the science advice provided. Thus, there is a need to find a balance. Researchers tasked with giving science-advice should engage in dialogues, co-creation activities etc. In order to understand context of the challenges and opportunities/solutions and the divergence of experiences, interests and solutions between stakeholders. However, they should also apply their scientific rigour in terms of reproducibility, independence, clarity in methods and science-based evidence, uncertainty etc. to the actual science advice produced and communicated. This should not eventually be a compromise between opinions expressed by stakeholders.

Transparency and accessibility are additional areas requiring attention. Many SPSI activities lack clarity in their processes and decision-making frameworks, which can lead to perceptions of bias or exclusion. Moreover, interactions and dialogue between researchers and stakeholders as to how to formulate advice to policy makers should be transparent and open in order to avoid doubt of the researchers' integrity and possible bias towards -or against-certain stakeholder interests. Clear communication about objectives, methods, and expected outcomes is essential to build stakeholder confidence. Furthermore, scientific outputs must be made accessible to non-experts. Complex terminology and dense technical documents can alienate policymakers and other stakeholders, limiting their ability to engage meaningfully. Simplified summaries, policy briefs, and visual tools such as infographics and

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decision trees can help bridge this gap, ensuring that scientific knowledge is actionable and readily understood by all participants.

The institutional design of SPSIs also warrants improvement. Many activities operate within rigid bureaucratic structures that hinder flexibility and innovation. There is a need for more adaptive governance models that allow researchers to respond dynamically to changing circumstances and emerging issues. This requires fostering cross-sectoral collaboration and breaking down institutional silos. Establishing dedicated intermediary organizations or boundary-spanning roles can facilitate coordination and communication across different sectors and disciplines. These intermediaries can act as translators between science and policy, ensuring that scientific evidence is effectively integrated into policy frameworks and vice versa.

A recurring theme in the analysis is the challenge of aligning timelines between science and policy. Scientific research often operates on longer timeframes than policymaking, which is frequently constrained by short-term political cycles. This misalignment can lead to frustration on both sides and impede the translation of research findings into actionable policies. To address this, SPSIs must develop mechanisms to harmonize these timelines. One potential solution is the adoption of iterative and modular approaches to research, where preliminary findings are shared early and updated as new evidence emerges. This approach enables policymakers to make informed decisions without waiting for the completion of lengthy studies, while still benefiting from the rigor of scientific inquiry.

It should be noted that in the ideal world of SPSI, there is continuous research on topics of – also future – practical and policy relevance. Thus, the main knowledge input to policy making should be based on existing results from e.g. participatory research on soil management as part of cropping systems. Therefore, the challenge of aligning the timing of policy and research is mostly relevant when new topics of interest appear at the political level before the research communities have produced sufficient knowledge in the knowledge area in focus. In the case of sustainable soil management, the EJP Soil and national programmes have preceded the Mission Soil, which has also initiated research projects and LLs before the finalization of the Soil Monitoring Law. Thus, at the time of implementation in national/regional regulations and possible adjustments of the next CAP, there may already be important scientific and practical knowledge (including in co-creation) to build a SPSI on.

The funding structures underpinning SPSI activities also require reform. Many interfaces are constrained by limited or short-term funding, which restricts their ability to plan and implement long-term initiatives. Sustainable financing models are essential to ensure the continuity and impact of activities. This could involve diversifying funding sources, such as leveraging public-private

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partnerships or engaging philanthropic organizations. Additionally, funding mechanisms should be designed to support not only scientific research but also the participatory processes and capacity-building activities that are critical to the success of SPSIs.

Improving the monitoring and evaluation of SPSI activities is another critical area. Despite the proliferation of interfaces, there is often a lack of systematic evaluation to assess their effectiveness and impact. This hampers the ability to learn from past experiences and refine approaches. Developing standardized metrics and frameworks for evaluating SPSIs can address this gap. Such evaluations should consider not only immediate outputs, such as policy briefs or stakeholder engagement events, but also longer-term outcomes, such as changes in policy, behaviour, and environmental conditions. Incorporating feedback loops into these evaluations can help SPIs adapt and improve continuously.

Capacity building among stakeholders is another area where SPSIs can be strengthened. Effective participation in SPSIs requires a certain level of knowledge and skills, which many stakeholders, particularly those from marginalized groups, may lack. Providing targeted training and resources can empower these stakeholders to engage more effectively. For policymakers, this might involve workshops on interpreting scientific data and understanding uncertainty. For scientists, training on communication, stakeholder engagement, and policy processes can enhance their ability to contribute to SPSIs. Addressing this requires deliberate efforts to build relationships and create safe spaces for dialogue. Facilitation techniques, conflict resolution strategies, and the establishment of shared goals can help overcome these barriers. Trust-building is not a one-time effort but an ongoing process that must be nurtured throughout the lifespan of an interface. Stakeholder platforms must become more forward-looking and adaptive to emerging challenges. Many interfaces are reactive, addressing issues only after they become pressing. A more proactive approach would involve horizon scanning and scenario planning to anticipate future challenges and opportunities. By incorporating foresight into their activities, SPSIs can help policymakers develop strategies that are not only effective in the short term but also resilient in the face of long-term uncertainties.

5. Soil Health Living Labs

The SHLLs are being developed as user centric approaches to enable the evidence-based decisions at different levels. The concept of SHLL is still in the process of the negotiations for the definitions, aims, activities, roles of actors. The functions of the SHLLs are in the defining stage mainly drawing experiences from other living labs like urban (Kris Steen & Bueren, 2017), agro-ecology (Mcphee et al., 2021), agri-food systems (Hvitsand et al., 2022). The main defined aims of SHLL are co-creation and formal learning to improve the soil health related ecosystem services. Other aims of innovations, formal learning and replication; and activities include development co-creation and iteration, with all the stakeholders are falling in the functions of the SPSIs (INREA-PREPSOIL, 2024). These aims can be better achieved if the living labs establish learning and feedback mechanisms such as SPSI to translate the evidence generated from the activities into soil health governance processes (Bhatta et al., 2024). The SHLLs creates unique opportunity to co-produce the knowledge and further translate this into governance process through science policy interfaces mechanisms. The key actors that generate the knowledge (scientists and other actors), and consume the knowledge (land users, policy, administrative) are partners from the beginning in the SHLLs with clear mandates to identity and address the challenges in the real and regional context. The analysis presented below is conducted from the selected literature on the living labs (82 publications) to identify the trends, activates and benefits, operationalisation of LL, stakeholder interactions models, lessons and outlook of the living labs.

5.1. PREPSOIL Contribution

The PREPSOIL project consortium is involved in developing crucial steps to guide the partners in establishing the SHLLs. As a first step, the partners co-developed a conceptual framework to define the core aims, activities, functions for the different land use type living labs (INREA-PREPSOIL, 2024). These differential features of LL for soil health in areas with specific land use, i.e. agricultural lands, cities, industrial lands and brownfields. For each land use, specific aims, activities, types of participants and contexts were described. They are core elements helpful to design new LLs or to orient existing ones towards improving soil health. They help frame the orchestration between the many stakeholders and discrepant concerns and ensure the connectedness between similar or complementary initiatives. The features are foreseen to be enriched and evolve thanks to the sharing of experience and practice among the actors. This conceptual framework has been applied in the co-development of the taxonomy, identification and mapping for living labs to feed into an online

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interactive atlas (Giulia & Ylla, 2024a, 2024b). Further, a business model plan canvas is developed to assist the partners in developing a detailed business plans while establishing the LLs (Alberto & Michelle, 2024). These two crucial guidelines are co-developed with various partners that will be beneficial to multiple users. Finally, an interactive atlas with the database of the active SHLLs and LLs are being organised in the PREPSOIL website. As part of the Soil Mission funded projects, the PREPSOIL partners also involved in the sister projects of NATIOONS that is dedicated to support the establishment of the SHLLs (Figure 11). These collaborative efforts have benefitted in interacting with a large number of stakeholders across EU those are interested in the SHLL.

Soil health living labs definition (EU Soil Mission, 2024): User-centered, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and co-design, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption.

Figure 11: Functions of the Soil Health living Labs
 Source: NATIOONS project

5.2. Activities and Benefits of SHLL

The development and operationalization of living labs have evolved significantly since their inception, reflecting broader shifts in research methodologies, stakeholder engagement, and focus areas such as soil health, land governance, and agri-food systems. This evolution, driven by increased funding opportunities and the active participation of diverse stakeholders, highlights the living labs' role as dynamic spaces for experimentation, co-creation, and sustainability transitions. Initially, living labs emerged as collaborative platforms aimed at fostering innovation through real-world experimentation and stakeholder participation. Their establishment was characterized by activities that prioritized defining objectives, stakeholder roles, and long-term sustainability. Early living labs were often supported by public-private partnerships, national grants, and EU funding, such as the Horizon 2020 program (Potters et al., 2022). These early labs focused on engaging multiple actors, including government bodies, research institutions, and local communities, to align their vision and objectives, ensuring that co-created solutions addressed specific regional needs (Beaudoin et al., 2022). Funding played a critical role in the early stages of establishing living labs. Public funding sources, such as EU grants, national agricultural schemes, and private sector investments, were crucial in providing the financial stability needed to initiate these projects. For instance, the ALL-Ready project, which aimed to create a European network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, was supported by EU funding to ensure long-term sustainability and stakeholder engagement (Gerald et al., 2024). Such funding mechanisms also facilitated the establishment of SHLLs, focusing on regenerative agriculture, carbon sequestration, and soil biodiversity (Bouma & Veerman, 2022).

The establishment of SHLLs represented a significant shift towards addressing soil health challenges within the context of sustainable land governance (Löbmann et al., 2022). These labs prioritized soil health indicators such as organic matter content, soil structure, water retention, and erosion control. With the growing emphasis on the EU Soil Mission and the development of soil health frameworks, SHLLs became critical platforms for testing sustainable agricultural practices and enhancing ecosystem services (Bouma & Veerman, 2022). Their establishment involved extensive stakeholder participation, including farmers, policymakers, researchers, and agricultural cooperatives, ensuring a holistic approach to soil management (Reijneveld et al., 2024). The benefits of these activities again linked with the broader categories of the governance and policy support, co-creation, capacity building, Innovation, sustainability and environmental impact (refer Figure 12 for additional information). These benefits are direct result of engagement with actors in diverse settings.

Figure 12: Benefits of the living labs

Source: Author

5.3. Operationalization and Research Activities

As living labs matured, their focus shifted from establishment to operationalization, marked by iterative prototyping, real-world experimentation, and continuous stakeholder engagement. The operationalization phase involved refining co-created solutions based on stakeholder feedback and real-world testing of innovations, including technologies, products, and services. Iterative feedback loops became central to the success of living labs, ensuring that solutions were adaptable to evolving needs and challenges (Schuurman & Leminen, 2021). For instance, urban living labs conducted iterative prototyping of sustainable housing solutions, mobility systems, and energy-saving technologies, ensuring that these solutions were refined through real-time stakeholder input (Alexandrakis, 2021).

In the context of soil health and agri-food systems, the operationalization of living labs often involved field trials, particularly in agricultural settings. These trials tested agro ecological practices, precision agriculture tools, and soil management techniques under real-world conditions (Bouma & Veerman, 2022). The use of advanced technologies, such as multispectral sensors, satellite imagery, and AI-driven models, enabled living labs to monitor soil health, biodiversity, and agricultural productivity, providing empirical evidence of the effectiveness of sustainable practices (Alexandrakis, 2021; Gardezi et al., 2024). This empirical focus was complemented by participatory approaches, where farmers,

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researchers, and local stakeholders collaborated in workshops, co-design sessions, and experimental trials to co-create and test innovations (Bhatta et al., 2024).

Research activities within living labs also evolved to include systematic literature reviews, comparative case studies, and longitudinal monitoring, reflecting the increasing complexity of sustainability challenges. Systematic reviews provided insights into the state of research on living labs, identifying gaps and trends, particularly in agri-food systems and soil governance (Hossain et al., 2019). Long-term monitoring of living lab outcomes, particularly in soil health, became essential for understanding the impact of co-created solutions on ecosystem services and sustainability transitions (Berberi et al., 2023; Mcphee et al., 2021). In recent years, the role of participation in living labs has expanded, emphasizing multi-stakeholder engagement, transdisciplinary research, and the co-creation of solutions that are both socially and environmentally sustainable. Participation in living labs now extends beyond traditional stakeholders to include local communities, farmers, policymakers, and industry representatives, ensuring that solutions are co-created in a manner that addresses local needs and promotes inclusivity (Bouma & Veerman, 2022). This is particularly evident in soil health living labs, where farmers play a critical role in testing and refining sustainable farming practices, ensuring that these practices are scalable and practical for real-world application.

The evolution of research activities in living labs has been marked by an increasing reliance on advanced technologies, participatory research methods, and real-world experimentation (Table 9). From early co-creation workshops to the sophisticated use of sensors and AI in soil health labs, the development of living labs reflects a broader trend towards integrating research, innovation, and practical solutions for sustainable land governance and agri-food systems. With continued support from funding bodies and an emphasis on stakeholder participation, living labs are likely to remain at the forefront of sustainability research, offering valuable insights into the practical challenges of achieving long-term ecosystem resilience. As the focus on soil health intensifies through initiatives like the EU Soil Mission, living labs are poised to play an increasingly important role in co-creating solutions that enhance ecosystem services, promote sustainable agriculture, and improve land governance practices.

Table 9: Research Activities carried out in SHLL

Research Activities
Systematic literature reviews to identify gaps, frameworks, and trends in the living labs field, specifically focused on agri-food systems, soil governance, and urban sustainability.
Long-term monitoring and evaluation of living lab outcomes, particularly focusing on sustainability transitions in soil and land governance or agri-food systems.

Participatory research approaches, including stakeholder interviews, focus groups, and workshops, to gather data on living lab performance and user engagement.

Design and execution of field experiments, including the use of sensors, satellite imagery, and AI-driven models to monitor agricultural productivity, soil health, and ecosystem services.

Comparative analysis of case studies across different living lab contexts, including urban, rural, and agricultural labs, to understand the diversity of approaches and outcomes.

Text mining and data coding to analyse the impact and evaluation of living labs from a meta-analysis of global literature.

Experimental design using novel methodologies such as serious games and participatory design tools to engage stakeholders and test agricultural and urban innovations in real-world contexts.

Source: Author

5.4. Stakeholder Interaction Models in SHLL

The SHLLs provide unique spaces where multiple stakeholders collaborate to develop and test innovative solutions in real-world environments. The stakeholder interaction models within these labs are crucial to their success, as they influence how knowledge is shared, innovations are co-created, and solutions are scaled.

Quadruple Helix and Public-Private-People Partnerships: One of the most widely applied stakeholder interaction models in Living Labs is the Quadruple Helix model, which emphasizes collaboration between four key sectors: academia, industry, government, and civil society (Nguyen & Marques, 2021). This model is designed to foster open innovation through shared governance and decision-making processes. In many cases, stakeholders participate equally, ensuring that innovations reflect diverse perspectives and needs (Laborgne et al., 2021). For example, it was highlighted that how multi-actor networks involving government, businesses, NGOs, and citizens successfully co-create sustainable food system solutions (Schafer, 2024; Wascher D. et al., 2023). The Public-Private-People Partnerships model is a variant of the Quadruple Helix model, adding a specific focus on citizen involvement (Hossain et al., 2019). This model ensures that the public, as end-users of innovations, plays an active role in co-designing and co-developing solutions. For instance, (Mbatha & Musango, 2022) discuss how energy sector living labs utilize 4Ps to bring together end-users, businesses, and public authorities, enabling a participatory approach to sustainable energy transitions.

Community-Based and Bottom-Up Innovation Models: A significant number of Living Labs, especially those in rural areas or focusing on localized sustainability challenges, adopt community-based and bottom-up innovation models. These models emphasize the role of local actors in driving innovation processes and tailoring solutions to the specific needs of their communities (Soini et al., 2023; Veronika Zavratic 2019) . Local knowledge, context-specific challenges, and community leadership

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are central to these models, ensuring that innovations are not only relevant but also sustainable in the long run. In rural contexts, such as in the agri-food sector, these models allow for more tailored interventions that address local ecological and socio-economic conditions (Gardezi et al., 2024; Rizzo et al., 2021). In agro-ecological systems, for example, community actors, including farmers and local businesses, are at the forefront of experimentation and co-creation (Gamache et al., 2020). The importance of these models lies in their ability to empower communities to take ownership of innovation processes, thereby fostering resilience and long-term sustainability.

Stakeholder-Led Experimentation Models: Stakeholder-led experimentation models position stakeholders, particularly end-users, as leaders in the innovation process. These models often delegate significant control over the design, implementation, and outcomes of experiments to the stakeholders, such as farmers in agricultural Living Labs or citizens in urban sustainability labs (Gamache et al., 2020; Toffolini et al., 2021; Toffolini et al., 2023). In these cases, stakeholders are not merely participants but are integral to shaping the direction of innovation, ensuring that the outcomes are directly relevant to their contexts and challenges. It shows that how can agricultural Living Labs provide farmers with the autonomy to lead trials of new farming systems, enabling them to apply their expertise and test practical solutions in real-world settings. This model fosters a sense of ownership among stakeholders, leading to greater engagement and more effective implementation of innovations.

Learning and Capacity-Building Models: Many Living Labs adopt learning and capacity-building models that focus on enabling stakeholders to learn from one another, build new skills, and enhance their capacity to engage in innovation processes effectively (Bhatta et al., 2025; Hvitsand et al., 2022). These models emphasize knowledge transfer, social learning, and skill-building as critical components of the innovation process. In agro-ecological Living Labs, it was described how stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, and agricultural advisors, participate in knowledge exchange sessions and co-create new agricultural practices (Bhatta et al., 2025; Hvitsand et al., 2022). These labs act as platforms for collective learning, where stakeholders not only develop innovations but also enhance their understanding of sustainability practices and governance mechanisms.

Citizen Science and Participatory Data Collection Models: Citizen Science and participatory data collection models involve citizens in the research and data collection process, often using low-cost technologies or mobile apps to gather data relevant to ongoing Living Lab projects (Laborgne et al., 2021; Veeckman & Temmerman, 2021). These models democratize the data collection process, enabling citizens to contribute directly to scientific research and policy development. In urban

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sustainability labs, for example, citizens participate in monitoring environmental conditions such as flood risks or air quality, providing valuable data for policymakers and researchers to analyse (Bronson et al., 2021). This model fosters greater transparency and inclusivity in the research process, as citizens not only provide data but are also involved in interpreting the results and developing subsequent interventions.

Boundary-Spanning and Knowledge Brokerage Models: In some cases, Living Labs adopt boundary-spanning and knowledge brokerage models, where certain stakeholders act as intermediaries, facilitating communication and knowledge exchange between different sectors or groups (Geenhuizen, 2018). These actors, often referred to as knowledge brokers or boundary spanners, play a critical role in ensuring that innovations are co-created effectively and applied across different domains. For instance, (Geenhuizen, 2018) describes how boundary-spanning organizations in Living Labs bridge gaps between policymakers, researchers, and private sector actors, facilitating collaboration and ensuring that innovations are relevant to all stakeholders involved. These models are particularly effective in complex multi-stakeholder environments where coordination and knowledge exchange are essential for success.

Innovation Ecosystem and Network Governance Models: Innovation ecosystem and network governance models create collaborative ecosystems where stakeholders operate within a shared governance structure, co-creating and implementing innovations (Prisco, 2024). These models emphasize the importance of networked governance, where decision-making is distributed among stakeholders, ensuring that innovations are developed and scaled through collective efforts. For example, (Prisco, 2024) describe how Turin's Living Lab brings together public institutions, private companies, and citizens to co-create solutions for smart cities and sustainable mobility. These ecosystems rely on collaborative governance structures to manage innovation processes, ensuring that stakeholders have an equal role in shaping the outcomes.

Reflexive and Adaptive Stakeholder Engagement Models: Finally, reflexive and adaptive stakeholder engagement models encourage continuous reflection and adaptation of stakeholder roles, processes, and innovations to ensure that they remain relevant and effective (Ane & Stine, 2014; McCrory et al., 2022). These models prioritize flexibility and adaptability, allowing stakeholder interactions to evolve as innovations develop and contexts change. In agroecology and precision agriculture Living Labs, reflexive processes are crucial for adapting innovations to changing environmental conditions and stakeholder needs. Stakeholders are encouraged to reflect on their roles, the co-creation process, and

the outcomes of experiments, allowing for continuous improvement and greater alignment with sustainability goals.

The diversity of stakeholder interaction models in Living Labs underscores the importance of collaboration, co-creation, and knowledge sharing in driving the innovation. Each model offers unique advantages depending on the context, goals, and stakeholders involved. Whether through the Quadruple Helix model, community-based innovation, or boundary-spanning approaches, Living Labs demonstrate the potential of participatory innovation processes to address complex challenges in sectors such as agri-food systems, urban sustainability, and energy transitions. Moving forward, the ability of Living Labs to foster meaningful stakeholder engagement will be crucial in ensuring that innovations are not only effective but also sustainable and inclusive.

5.5. Lessons and Outlook for the SHLL

The growing body of research on LLs highlights their potential as platforms for fostering innovation, driving sustainability transitions, and engaging diverse stakeholders in the co-creation of solutions to complex socio-environmental challenges. The systematic analysis reveals a range of insights related to governance, stakeholder engagement, sustainability, scalability, and evaluation. Despite the progress made, several challenges remain that require addressing to fully harness the potential of LLs in different contexts, particularly in soil, land governance, and agri-food systems.

Governance and Institutional Support: Effective governance and inclusive stakeholder engagement are paramount to the success of LLs. The LLs require robust governance frameworks to manage the complexity of multi-actor environments and ensure long-term sustainability (Gerald et al., 2024), promotes equitable participation among diverse actors (Mbatha & Musango, 2022). The ability of LLs to span boundaries between different sectors and organizations is highlighted as essential for transferring knowledge and fostering innovation, particularly in urban and agricultural settings (Geenhuizen, 2018). However, many LLs struggle with institutional integration, limiting their ability to scale up and embed innovations in broader policy frameworks (Bulkeley et al., 2016). Without strong governance and long-term financial backing, LLs often face challenges in maintaining engagement and achieving their objectives (Reijneveld et al., 2024). In the agri-food sector, LLs have shown potential to promote sustainable practices, but their success depends on collective action and the alignment of governance structures with local needs (Gamache et al., 2020).

Governance challenges in LLs often stem from the complexity of managing multi-actor settings, particularly when stakeholders have differing objectives, levels of influence, or interests. To mitigate

these issues, recommendations suggest the adoption of transparent stakeholder recruitment processes and clearly defined roles for participants to avoid ambiguity (Leminen et al., 2015; Schuurman & Leminen, 2021). Furthermore, strengthening public-private partnerships is crucial for ensuring broad engagement and impact (Gascó, 2017; Potters et al., 2022). Another key recommendation is the need to build trust among stakeholders, which can be fostered through regular and transparent communication (Laborgne et al., 2021). Trust-building mechanisms, such as participatory decision-making and early involvement of stakeholders, have been shown to enhance the legitimacy of LL activities, especially in sensitive contexts like agri-food systems and soil governance (Bouma & Veerman, 2022; Reijneveld et al., 2024). Moreover, inclusivity must be a priority, with marginalized groups and smaller actors, such as smallholder farmers, being actively involved in decision-making processes to ensure that their needs are reflected in the innovation process (Trivellas et al., 2023).

Facilitating Co-Creation and Stakeholder Engagement: One of the defining characteristics of LLs is their user-centric approach to innovation, where end-users are actively involved in the co-creation process. However, managing user engagement is not without challenges, especially when participants are passive or disengaged (Schuurman & Leminen, 2021). To enhance user involvement, recommendations suggest providing greater flexibility in the roles assigned to participants, allowing them to shift from passive to more proactive positions throughout the project lifecycle (Bouzarovski et al., 2023). Early user involvement is particularly crucial for fostering trust, improving innovation uptake, and ensuring that solutions are tailored to user needs. This can be facilitated by offering training and capacity-building workshops that equip users with the skills needed to contribute meaningfully to the innovation process (Bouwma et al., 2022; Potters et al., 2022). Many studies emphasize that LLs are most successful when they empower users to take proactive roles in the co-creation process, allowing for more radical and transformative innovations. However, stakeholder engagement in LLs often faces barriers related to power dynamics. The need for LLs to address power imbalances that prevent marginalized groups from participating fully in decision-making processes is identified (Bronson et al., 2021; Nguyen & Marques, 2021).

Promoting Cross-sectoral Collaboration and Policy Integration: Living labs operate at the intersection of multiple sectors, requiring cross-sectoral collaboration to address the complex challenges they seek to solve. The need for deeper collaboration has been identified between local governments, businesses, and citizens to ensure that innovations address both technical and social challenges. Cross-sectoral partnerships are particularly important in sectors such as agri-food systems and urban

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development, where challenges like sustainability transitions and climate adaptation require coordinated action across different levels of governance (von Wirth et al., 2018). By doing so, LLs can ensure that their experimental outcomes are institutionalized and contribute to long-term policy change. Similarly, integrating LL outcomes into national policy frameworks, such as the EU's agricultural and environmental policies, can help scale innovations across regions and ensure that they contribute to systemic change (Schafer, 2024; Wascher D. et al., 2023).

Scalability, Funding and Impact: One of the major challenges identified is the difficulty of scaling innovations developed in living labs. While LLs are effective at generating localized solutions, many studies point out that scaling these solutions to broader contexts remains problematic (Bouzarovski et al., 2023). Scalability also depends on the ability of LLs to foster cross-sectoral collaboration, integrating diverse perspectives and knowledge systems to address complex sustainability challenges. The literature highlights the importance of engaging policymakers, businesses, and civil society in the scaling process to ensure that innovations can be adapted to different regional and sectoral contexts. Another major obstacle in establishing and sustaining LLs is the lack of long-term financial support and institutional backing. Many LLs are initiated through short-term projects with limited funding, leading to concerns about their sustainability beyond the pilot phase. To address this, scholars recommend the development of match-funding mechanisms that pool resources from municipalities, the private sector, and international institutions (Schafer, 2024; Wascher D. et al., 2023). Institutionalizing LLs within regional and national governance structures is another critical strategy for securing sustainability. By embedding LL activities within existing policy frameworks, such as those related to SDGs and soil mission objectives, LLs can gain more stable financial support and legitimacy. Furthermore, ensuring alignment between LLs and broader policy frameworks allows for the scaling of successful innovations, increasing their impact beyond the local (Bouma & Veerman, 2022).

The success of SHLLs depends on several critical factors, including strong governance, effective stakeholder engagement, robust evaluation frameworks, and the ability to scale innovations. LLs face challenges related to power dynamics, financial sustainability, and institutional integration, but they offer valuable lessons for addressing complex socio-environmental challenges across diverse sectors. Governance and stakeholder engagement must be strengthened through clear communication, trust-building, and equitable participation, while long-term sustainability hinges on securing stable funding and integrating LLs within broader governance frameworks. Robust evaluation frameworks are essential for measuring the full impact of LL activities, and user engagement can be enhanced through flexible roles, creative tools, and strong feedback loops. Furthermore, cross-sectoral collaboration and

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digital innovation are key to scaling LLs and ensuring their relevance in addressing complex challenges like soil and land governance, agri-food systems, and urban sustainability transitions. By implementing these recommendations, LLs can become more effective platforms for innovation and contribute meaningfully to sustainability transitions. As LLs continue to evolve, future research must focus on overcoming these challenges to fully realize the transformative potential of living labs.

6. Co-Development of Enhanced Science Policy Society Practices

The following sections present discussions between researchers and other stakeholders facilitated by PREPSOIL at a series of workshop sessions addressing the relation between Living Lab activities in co-creation of improved soil management and science -policy- society interfaces.

6.1. Review of Methods and Tools to Establish and Operationalise the Science Policy Society Interfaces

The session “The Role of Science Policy Interactions: Visions for Transformation Pathways in the Soil Health Living Labs” was organised at the Agroecosystems in Transformation: Visions, Technologies and Actors Landscapes Conference, Berlin. The research results from the literature review and the user needs for the policy information from the soil needs assessments were presented to the audience representing research, science-policy, Living lab, policy, and soil health governance. The participants were asked several questions through collaborative tool mentimeter. These questions are designed to identify the different of roles of actors, challenges they face in the SPSI and LL contexts. In addition, the discussion was enhanced through other presentations ranging from the models of the knowledge exchange at the living labs to the best practices of soil information sharing in the rural science policy stakeholder platforms. The key outcome of the collaborative discussion is the refined framework of the SPSI, identification of best-of-practice methods for SPSI functions at the national/regional level. The participants in this workshop identified themselves to be part of ongoing and future living labs with different capacities and roles that is essential for the living labs success (Table 10). These multiple roles of the researchers were categorised into 4 functions of the SPSI that reflect the possible roles by the researchers involved in the living labs (Refer to section 4.4 for the details of the functions). Each of the SPSI function requires different expertise from the participants involved in the LL. These observations show the similar trends, where multiple functions of the knowledge brokers have been identified (Cvitanovic et al.). The participants, particularly actors from research indicate their different roles in the settings of co-production, user-centric LLs, that goes beyond the convention’s researcher role (Cvitanovic et al., 2024).

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Table 10: Roles and activities identified by the participants in the workshop

Function of SPSI	Roles and activities mentioned by the participants
Stakeholder Platform	Facilitating Collaboration, Coordinator, Engagement, Relationships Management, Stakeholder Engagement
Knowledge Generation	Researcher/Scientist, Subject matter expert, External Researcher, Monitoring and Assessment, Knowledge Mobilization, Leadership, Technology Expert
Knowledge Management	Capacity Building, Business Implementation, Data base experts
Knowledge Brokering	Observer, Reflection, Accompanying External, Learner, Manage the relationships

Source: Author

When asked about the challenges in the functions of SPSI, participants mentioned a range of challenges that affect the generation, synthesis, and transfer of evidence when working in the LLs. A significant challenge lies in community cohesion and the co-definition of goals, as these processes require aligning diverse stakeholders with varied perspectives and priorities. The complexity of the process and evidence relativity further complicate matters, as findings are often context-specific and may not easily translate across different settings. These pragmatic challenges indicate the need for the update of the skill set of the researchers to match with the expectations from the participation in the LLs. (Ghent Group, 2024) is an example showing the structure of the capacity building programs for the researchers in the SPSI. Additionally, epistemological differences—the ways in which different participants understand and value knowledge—can hinder consensus and cohesion. The participation of various actors, including non-experts, introduces another layer of complexity, as their input is essential for inclusivity but may lack technical depth, requiring careful facilitation. The carefully designed co-production in the LL when worked with knowledge brokers would enable such facilitation to include different forms of scientific and practical knowledge.

The generalization of findings and synthesizing diverse cases poses further challenges, as they demand the synthesis tools application, ability to draw out common themes from distinct situations without oversimplifying or losing essential details. Evidence transfer is further constrained by inflexible systems that resist adaptation and by the format of information, which may not be easily accessible or understandable to all stakeholders. This issue is compounded by a lack of long-term perspectives and monitoring structures, which are essential for tracking evidence and maintaining relevance over time. Additionally, the lack of skills required by the researchers for effective evidence synthesis and transfer can impede progress, particularly when technical expertise is needed to convey findings to diverse audiences. Together, these challenges underscore the need for strategic approaches that foster adaptability, inclusivity, and continuous capacity building within Living Labs.

Figure 13: Different research methods and tools implemented in the SPSIs
 Source: Author

Participants emphasized that researchers involved in the LL must embody a combination of analytical skills and subject expertise to contribute effectively to collaborative, real-world problem-solving. The capacity for synthesis and fact-checking is essential, as researchers must navigate complex, interdisciplinary information and distil it into actionable insights. A strong local understanding and farmer-oriented approach were also highlighted as critical, as these enable researchers to tailor their work to the specific needs and contexts of the communities they serve. The integration of citizen science approaches further reinforces this community-centric focus, encouraging researchers to engage directly with local stakeholders and incorporate their insights into scientific processes.

Equally important are soft skills that foster open communication and inclusivity within the diverse environments of LLs. Traits such as humility, patience, and openness to other perspectives allow researchers to listen actively and engage meaningfully with varied stakeholders, including non-experts. The ability to communicate effectively, using easy-to-understand language, ensures that research findings are accessible to all involved parties. Additionally, curiosity and an open-minded attitude support researchers in embracing interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary perspectives, which are necessary for addressing complex issues that span multiple domains. Together, these characteristics create a collaborative atmosphere that enhances the researcher’s capacity to contribute to the dynamic and integrative nature of LLs.

6.2. Challenges and Opportunities in Establishing Science-Policy Interfaces at Soil Health Living Labs

The participants are about 30 researchers from PREPSOIL project representing the land use types-agriculture, Forestry, Urban/Post-Industrial, and Mixed. A concept note was shared with the task leaders and organisers. The starting point for this co-development workshop is a presentation of status of the research methods from the desk-based literature review. The participants were organised into 3 breakout groups-agriculture, forest and mixed, and Urban, used the online tool (Mural) to co-develop the main functions of the science policy interfaces and challenges in relation to the soil health living labs. The following questions were addressed in the [Mural here](#).

- What is the purpose/Needs for establishing/improving Science Policy Interface at the living labs for you?
- Which impact would you like to achieve from Science Policy Interface at the Living Labs?
- Which support, trainings, or partnerships do you need to involve in the science policy interface at the living labs?
- Challenges in this process: Challenges you might face in establishing and implementing the science policy interfaces at the living labs?

The SHLLs provide experimental environments where scientific research is directly translated into practical applications. However, effectively integrating SPSIS into these settings is essential for translating soil health findings into impactful policies. The observations from these co-designing process is analysed and presented for each of the land use types in the below sections. This analysis presents the emerging themes identified during a workshop with scientists and researchers. These themes encompass insights from SHLL to SPSIs, required supports, and challenges for SPSIs within LLs focusing on agriculture, forest and mixed, urban, and post-industrial land uses.

6.2.1. Insights from SHLL to SPSI

Agriculture: The participants focusing on the agricultural sector perceived SPSIs within LLs as pivotal for resource mobilization and for advising on policy initiatives in support of scaling sustainable practices. Their rationale was that, outcomes of LLs may become aligned with broader agricultural policy objectives and possibly secure funding for support. Thus, if it becomes a policy objective to mainstream sustainable soil management practices, the LLs may identify such practices and options for scaling these partly supported by policies. Furthermore, regional insights derived from LLs can offer valuable guidance for shaping legislation tailored to local contexts, as these localized nuances are crucial for addressing specific agricultural challenges.

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Forest and Mixed: In forest and mixed land use contexts, there is a distinct focus on aligning LL outcomes with decision-making processes at the regional level. Participants noted that successful local administrative models could be transferred to other regions, emphasizing the need for SPSIs that bring scientific knowledge closer to policymakers. Moreover, the importance of planning considerations within LLs, particularly concerning wildfire management, was underscored as a critical factor in mitigating risks in forested and mixed landscapes. Effective SPIs should bridge the communication gaps between scientists and policymakers, ensuring that scientific outputs are sufficiently tailored to inform policy decisions effectively.

Urban and Post-Industrial: The primary impact envisioned for urban and post-industrial land uses is the role of LLs as testing grounds for innovative policies and practices that can be scaled to other areas. The integration of SPIs within these LLs facilitates experimentation with solutions that are both practical and legally feasible. By leveraging networks among local authorities, LLs can out-scale successful measures, fostering a broader adoption of sustainable practices. Furthermore, the early involvement of policymakers in LL discussions enables a better understanding of policy settings, enhancing the likelihood of policy acceptance. This approach allows for an iterative policy development process, informed by LL insights and stakeholder feedback.

6.2.2. Required Support, Trainings, and Partnerships for Effective SPSIs

Agriculture: The participants from the agriculture land use indicated the need to establish the SPSIs that connects the ongoing LLs with the relevant policy actors from regional to national level. These partnerships could facilitate the dissemination of LL findings into agricultural policy frameworks, particularly at regional and national levels. The participants agreed that the existing knowledge on agriculture soils could be better translated through the SPSIs through knowledge brokering and facilitation.

Forest and Mixed: Forest and mixed land uses suggested SPSIs that facilitate effective communication between scientists and policymakers. Developing targeted materials, such as concise policy briefs, was suggested to make scientific outputs accessible to policymakers. Additionally, it was suggested that engaging forest land users, producers and private sector companies may support policy advocacy efforts, as these stakeholders can help influence policy decisions. Societal involvement was also highlighted as a means of bolstering political support, suggesting that inclusive SPSIs could promote broader acceptance and integration of LL findings into policies.

Urban and Post-Industrial: For urban and post-industrial land uses, the establishment of collaborative working groups within the LLs was identified by the participants as a key support mechanism. These

groups should include scientists, LL practitioners, and policymakers, fostering an environment conducive to open dialogue and mutual understanding. The role of communication experts and knowledge brokers was emphasized by the partners to bridge the language barriers often present between scientific and policy discourses.

6.2.3. Challenges in Establishing and Implementing SPSI

Agriculture: Some participants mentioned that a significant challenge for agricultural SPSIs within LLs is navigating the complexities of land tenure systems and varying farm models. Effective SPSIs require knowledge brokers who understand the intricacies of local and regional agricultural practices, as well as windows of opportunity for policy influence, such as the renewal of the CAP. Aligning the scale of LL operations with policymaking levels is also critical, as mismatched scales may hinder the policy relevance of LL findings. Additionally, securing engagement from policymakers requires identifying the right stakeholders at opportune moments, especially within the European Union's complex political landscape.

Forest and Mixed: The primary communication challenges within forest and mixed land use SPSIs relate to delivering scientific messages effectively to policymakers. Traditional communication methods, such as policy briefs, often fail to capture policymakers' attention, necessitating more informal, direct interactions. Furthermore, the short-term focus of political agendas, driven by electoral cycles, often limits policymakers' willingness to engage with complex, long-term scientific findings. Consequently, framing LL outputs as concise, impactful messages that align with policymakers' priorities is essential for advancing forest and mixed land use objectives.

Urban and Post-Industrial: Urban and post-industrial SPSIs face the challenge of including the informal stakeholder exchanges with the formal structures that often accompanies contractual agreements. Participants noted that while informal dialogue fosters trust and collaboration, excessive formality can deter stakeholder engagement. It was suggested that initiating SPSI processes at the onset of a LL may prevent goal misalignment among diverse stakeholders. However, this would require that the different stakeholders actually do have the same interests and objectives when defining sustainable soil management, the responsibilities of soil manager's vis-à-vis policy makers and the market actors and how much compensation should be given from either the market or public support (CAP etc) for land users to apply costly practices. However, the dialogues under SPSI may serve to clarify differences as a step towards resolving conflicts of interest and aligning goals in the long term. Additionally, different stakeholders' wants and needs often clash, necessitating careful negotiation to foster a

collaborative environment. Therefore, early involvement and alignment of stakeholder objectives are crucial to ensure the effectiveness of SPIs within these land use contexts.

6.2.4. Conclusion

The successful establishment and implementation of SPIs within SHLLs necessitate a multifaceted approach that considers the unique challenges and opportunities across diverse land uses. While each context—agriculture, forest and mixed, urban, and post-industrial—presents specific requirements, common themes include the need for effective communication, stakeholder engagement, and timing. Agricultural SPIs must focus on regional-specific policy opportunities, while forest and mixed SPIs benefit from informal communication and advocacy efforts. Urban and post-industrial SPIs should leverage local networks and prioritize early stakeholder involvement. Addressing these needs through targeted supports, such as working groups and communication experts, will enhance the capacity of LLs to influence soil health policies effectively.

6.3. Identifying the best practices at the SHLLS

The PREPSOIL partners visited “The Gál Ecological Farm”, located in the Kiskunság National Park, southeast of Budapest, in Bugacpuszta, in which ÖMKI’s PREPSOIL Soil Needs Assessment took place. The farm is a member of ÖMKI’s on-farm living lab. The farm breeds Hungarian Grey cattle and joined soil-related experiments; plots for arable cropping are close to each other (renting pastures for cattle as well; using cover cropping tillage reduction (organic agriculture principles including integration of animals in arable cropping) intensively and trying no till which is quite challenging in organic farming. The partners from PREPSOIL organised a group discussion following the field visits. Several of the questions in the group discussion are linked with the interaction with the policy actors. These perceptions from the local farmers and researchers involved in the living labs are summarised below.

- The local stakeholders mentioned factors and preconditions important for healthy soil and crop management such as funding for on-farm experiments, communication with the decision makers (water management), and cooperation with other farming communities, investment and knowledge to create short supply chains, communication channels with consumers.
- Soil management practices suitable to climatic and farming conditions can be enhanced through cooperation between local farmers, water and soil advisors and researchers in a “dispersed” type of Living Lab, in this case under supervision of the NGO Ömki.
- Water regulations does not allow application of certain soil conservations measures (organic matter management and recycling of resources focusing on manure management and composting organic residues) that may be suitable to local conditions to enhance the water retention capacity, organic matter increase.

- A communication between local water management authorities has already been started. Clarification of needs and ways of handling different interests in decisions of water management must be worked out, if need be, by suggesting modifications on relevant legislation. This may be an example of LL meeting SPSI.
- Stakeholders appreciate the efforts of agricultural policy to promote the changes, but the ways of communication and implementation must be improved. For example, the local initiatives do not continue as the support was limited (projects/programs end).

This interaction with the local farmers and researchers highlights the need for the better and effective communication with different levels of ministries administration, bureaucracy and policy actors. The soil health improvement measures implementation involved trade-offs with existing water regulation. The farmers already established a farmers' association (stakeholder platform) and initiated the communication with the local policy and administration. The researchers from OMKI are acting as "knowledge brokers" by supporting the local farmers with the evidence from the field trials and creating the interaction spaces with the extension and policy actors (Soil needs assessments). However, the soil health improvement is a complex and long journey, needs a long-term collaboration, and needs to be institutionalised.

6.4. Policy Demands for the Regional Soil Health Governance in Brandenburg, Germany

A workshop with the regional level policy actors, implementing agencies, administrative actors is organised by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture to identify the synergies among the EU horizon projects through effective science to policy communication. Prof. Katharina Helming from ZALF gave a presentation on the ongoing Soil mission projects including the PREPSOIL, SOLO, BENCHMARKS. Participants from ZALF further coordinated a breakout group that discussed the synergies and science to policy transfer mechanisms. About 20 actors from research institutes, regional ministries, and administrative agencies attended the breakout group.

Various funding programs at EU, federal and state level offer a wide range of opportunities for financial support in the implementation of research and innovation projects. The complementary use of different programs can promote innovation along the entire value chain in complex, multi-year projects. The aim of the workshop is to demonstrate synergies between the EU funding program Horizon Europe and other funding programs. The example of the EU Soil Mission will be used to illustrate how stakeholders can implement their projects more effectively within the framework of

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Horizon Europe and how federal and state programs can support or expand the implementation of Horizon Europe projects.

1. The program planning level, i.e. how the various EU, federal and state programs (including EU structural and agricultural funds) can be linked together in a target-oriented manner under the given program planning conditions: Technical departments, administrative authorities of structural and agricultural policy, investment banks, economic development agencies, etc., which design and disseminate funding programs, as well as funding recipients (research institutions, companies, etc.) in their role as applicants.
2. The project level, i.e. how can different approaches from research and practice be strategically combined in projects to support the objectives of the soil mission?

Conclusions: The implementing and policy actors experience multiple projects at the same time, such as the current Soil Mission Projects. The implementing actors already gained a lot of experience in implementing EU Horizon, multi-year, stakeholder-based projects. The lessons gained are demonstrated in the skills of project management, coordination of the resources (regional funding), land users' mobilisation, and documentation. However, a considerable need was mentioned by these actors to develop the skills for synthesis and translation of the scientific evidence into actionable policy outcomes. The knowledge generated by the researchers, experience gained by the farmers, lessons learned by the implementing agencies at the regional level needs to be co-synthesised for the policy advice and design of future projects. Co-designing has been prioritised as a tool to implement while synthesising the lessons and challenges. The policy actors perceived the need to include the local communities in the assessments. The participatory assessments, field trials about the successful cases, demonstration sites and digitalisation has been identified as effective tools of the communication. The policy stakeholder identified several crucial needs from Brandenburg region that can be co-developed into future projects. These ideas include the research needs to understand the restoration mechanisms of the existing photovoltaic production sites, living labs at the post-mining landscapes, develop and test the technologies (robotics, digitalisation, spatial mapping, soil monitoring), innovative soil restoration measures and their monitoring (humus restoration, water saving, agroforestry), cost effective food consumption practices. The actors further identified that these ideas need co-designing with partners from business, start-ups, training agencies, knowledge brokers, digital technologies and most importantly active stakeholder platforms and networks (societal participation).

6.5. Validation of Research Results with Experts

The Ghent Group is an informal community of European institutes and professionals working on science-based advice on agriculture and agricultural policy within the framework of social, economic and environmental sustainability (Ghent Group, 2024). Its main goals are to network, share best practices and foster learning and teaching. The Group organized a workshop and its Annual Meeting in November 2024 in Brussels. The theme of the event was the role of science in addressing policy dilemmas and Living Labs as interfaces between science and policy. The workshop explored how LLs in agriculture, food, and the environment can be effective for policy development and innovation in policymaking processes. Around forty participants from several European Research and policy institutions joined the Living Labs workshop. Several examples of the relation between LLs and policy makers were presented and represented two different approaches: In one approach, using the term “policy labs”, the main purpose of the LL was to test potential policies in the agri-food system and use the “laboratory” to evaluate positive and negative outcomes for stakeholders before possibly out scaling a specific policy initiative (Mosaic; FEAST LL). The other approach was to demonstrate how experiences gained via co-creation by stakeholders focusing on a challenge (e.g. healthy diets for school children based on sustainably produced food sources regionally (ProDijj); testing new food processing practices with companies and consumers (FoodPilot); healthy soil management and Agroforestry (Prepsoil, AGROFORSYLL)) may point to needs for policy initiatives as a means to scaling out. This, again, requires a functional – and formal- organisation of SPSI (Ghent Group, 2024). The Prepsoil results from the literature review and other workshops were presented in a poster format to wider audience representing academia, experts in interfaces and living labs (Figure 14). The participants appreciated the results and encouraged to collaborate with ongoing living lab networks including agro-ecology and other urban living labs.

Co-Designing Science Policy Interfaces for Soil Health Living Labs

Soil health Living Labs provide co-creation opportunities where R&I can directly be translated into practical applications. However, effective science policy interfaces in LLs are essential for translating knowledge into policies, to improve framework conditions for healthy soil management. As part of Prepsails' development of LL best-practices co-designing workshops with scientists, policy makers, land users and living lab experts seek to identify how insights from LLs may provide science advice to policy makers.

Policy Interactions

Regional soil needs and challenges across 20 European regions demonstrated that while technical options and stakeholder motivations for improving soil management exists widely, there are barriers to overcome, which includes changing the framework conditions in markets and policy regulation. Soil health governance is driven by a combination of environmental/biophysical, socio-economic, political and technological changes. The regional policy actors gained management experience in implementing multiple soil related projects. However, upskilling needs for the knowledge synthesis, stakeholder management were identified to effectively implement future research and innovation projects through living labs.

Several challenges identified:

- Need for stakeholder engagement, effective communication and timing
- Needs for long-term funding and monitoring, and a strategy for the science policy interfaces
- Partnerships with policy makers arrives at later stages
- Aligning national policies with regional decision-making process
- Dialogues with LLs involved in Prepsails demonstrated a lack of specific processes for science-advice as a vehicle for improving framework conditions for soil management.

Achievements

Reviewing functions of the science policy interfaces at the soil health living labs.

Barriers:

- Develop procedures for ensuring the integrity of the science-based policy advice from LLs co-creation
- Lack of skills for effective evidence synthesis and transfer as dedicated science – advice based on LL co-creation while ensuring scientific integrity

Conditions for Lasting impact of the science-policy dialogue:

- Involve the policy makers/civil servants that have local understanding and farmer-oriented approach
- Collaborative networks with citizens and society, identify the right mix of policy makers
- Adaptation of principles-Credibility, Legitimacy, Relevance and Integrity
- Co-creation with the policy makers in the development

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Figure 14: Poster presented in Ghent Group

7. Guidelines to Establish and Operationalise the Science Policy Society Interfaces in the Soil Health Living Labs.

The analysis of SPSIs and SHLLs indicated many similarities with regards to their activities, theories used, models of stakeholder interaction, benefits, challenges, lessons and outlook indicated many similarities. This provides a synthesis of these similarities, and it presents a framework to establish and operationalise the SPSI. These concepts are useful to researchers who are already in the process of establishing of SHLLs or in the process of setting up SPSI in general.

7.1. Synergetic activities and research methods

The analysis compares the research activities planned and implemented in the SHLL and SPSIs, illustrating the synergies between these two frameworks in fostering collaborative, evidence-based innovation. The relationship indicates that the tools and methods employed in one domain inform and enhance the practices of the other. This interconnected approach underscores the importance of shared methodologies and collaborative processes in addressing complex soil health challenges. In the SPSIs, the focus is on activities that bridge knowledge gaps and facilitate the translation of scientific evidence into actionable policy and societal outcomes. Key activities include literature reviews, synthesis, and knowledge transfer, which are fundamental for collating and disseminating insights from diverse studies. Refer Figure 15 for detailed list of the activities. These processes enable stakeholders to identify patterns, draw generalizations, and inform decision-making. Furthermore, scenario and foresight approaches are highlighted as essential for anticipating future trends and challenges, allowing policymakers to adopt proactive strategies. The inclusion of integrated assessments and policy impact assessments emphasizes the importance of evaluating the broader implications of interventions, ensuring that they align with long-term sustainability goals.

In parallel, SHLLs prioritize on-the-ground experimentation and co-creation to address soil health challenges in specific contexts. Activities such as long-term field trials, on-farm trials, and participatory research are central to this approach, enabling researchers and practitioners to test and refine innovative practices in real-world settings. These activities are complemented using digital tools and platforms, which facilitate data collection, analysis, and dissemination, making the outcomes of SHLLs more accessible to a wider audience. The emphasis on user-centered innovation – ideally - ensures that the solutions developed are both practical and relevant to the needs of end-users, including farmers and local communities.

Figure 15: Research activities implemented in SPSIs and SHLLs

Source: Author

A notable overlap between SPSI and SHLLs is their shared commitment to collaborative evidence generation, capacity building and knowledge brokering. These activities foster the exchange of expertise and resources between stakeholders, creating a collaborative environment where diverse perspectives can converge. The emphasis on co-creation in both frameworks highlight the importance of engaging stakeholders in the design and implementation of solutions, ensuring that they are not only scientifically sound but also socially and politically feasible. This participatory approach enhances the relevance and scalability of innovations, increasing their likelihood of adoption. This synergetic relationship underscores the mutual reinforcement between SPSI and SHLLs. SPSI provides the frameworks and methodologies necessary for evidence synthesis and policy translation, while SHLLs offer practical, localized insights that enrich the broader knowledge base. By integrating these two initiatives, researchers can develop solutions that are both context-specific and applicable, addressing the complex, multifaceted challenges of soil health.

7.2. Co-designing methods and tools

The analysis also highlights the intersection of SPSI and SHLLs, focusing on their shared challenges and key research methods required to address them. It reveals that addressing sustainability challenges in SHLLs necessitates robust SPSI frameworks that bridge gaps between science, policy, and societal engagement. Refer Figure 16 for additional information on the challenges and research methods.

A prominent theme is the necessity of long-term engagement to ensure the successful implementation of science-policy collaborations within SHLLs. Challenges such as balancing scientific

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credibility with societal relevance and managing transparency, accountability, and trust are critical for fostering sustained partnerships. These challenges are compounded by institutional and bureaucratic barriers, which often introduce uncertainty into the process. Furthermore, stakeholder expectations and power dynamics must be managed effectively to maintain equitable participation and prevent imbalances in decision-making authority. These dynamics underscore the importance of inclusive and adaptive governance mechanisms that can respond to evolving needs over time.

The analysis also emphasizes the importance of planning, assessing and demonstrating impact as a central component of both SPSI and SHLLs. Evidence-based assessments are necessary to justify the relevance and utility of initiatives to policymakers and stakeholders. However, achieving this requires overcoming limitations in data availability and quality, as well as the development of capacity and knowledge transfer tools to ensure evidence can be translated into actionable strategies. A related challenge involves resource and capacity constraints, which are common in both domains and require innovative solutions to optimize limited resources for maximum impact.

From the SHLL perspective, sustainability is linked to several interdependent factors, including scalability of innovations, stakeholder engagement, and interdisciplinary collaboration. These elements are crucial for the co-creation and knowledge production processes inherent to living labs. The challenges of context-specific barriers and science-policy translation highlight the need for nuanced, localized approaches to implementation. Similarly, the integration of technological and data management tools into SHLL operations is essential to support the collection and dissemination of knowledge, enabling decision-makers to address challenges with greater precision.

Evaluation and impact assessment methods are highlighted as critical tools for understanding the effectiveness of interventions in both SPSI and SHLL contexts. Furthermore, research methods availability—including those that facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration—can ensure that efforts remain aligned with sustainability objectives. This interdependence suggests that advancing research capabilities within SHLLs can directly enhance the efficacy of SPSI frameworks, creating a positive feedback loop that benefits both domains. The analysis encapsulates the shared challenges and research priorities of SPSI and SHLLs. By addressing these challenges collectively, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can create innovative, sustainable solutions to the pressing issues faced by SHLLs, while strengthening the broader science-policy interface.

Figure 16: Challenges identified in the SPSI and SHLL
 Source: Author

7.3. Conclusions: Framework to Establish and Operationalise SPSI

In this concluding section, the synthesis is presented by combining all the evidence from the soil needs assessment, literature analysis of SPSI and SHLL, and co-development workshops. The authors propose a framework with key steps to establish and operationalise the SPSI in the SHLL. The steps presented below describes a guide to initiate the SPSI process in general and in the SHLL. In particular, the ongoing research from Soil Mission funded projects about the establishment framework, business models development, stakeholder engagement guidelines

1. **Mandate, Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement:** Begin by identifying and involving a diverse range of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, practitioners, and local communities. Use stakeholder mapping tools to ensure comprehensive representation. Establish a stakeholder platform for co-designing activities including the mandate for the interface through various activities, needs analysis, and dynamic interaction to promote inclusivity, and mutual understanding.
2. **Needs Assessment and Problem Definition:** Conduct a collaborative needs assessment to identify the key soil health challenges and policy gaps specific to the local context. Define clear and actionable objectives that align with regional policy goals and stakeholder priorities. This step ensures alignment between research objectives and practical needs.
3. **Co-Design Roles, Principles and Planning:** Facilitate co-creation workshops to design the SPSI framework, principles to be adapted and its research activities. Develop a roadmap that integrates scientific research, policy requirements, and societal input. Clearly outline roles and responsibilities, ensuring flexibility to adapt to emerging challenges and opportunities. The membership formats, governance mechanisms and decision-making processes can be co-designed with the partners.

4. **Evidence Generation:** Deploy participatory research methods, including modelling, scenario development, and long-term field trials, to generate robust evidence on soil health. Combine these with insights from literature reviews to create a comprehensive knowledge base. Use a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods to ensure evidence relevance across various scales.
5. **Evidence Synthesis and Assessment:** Co-develop and synthesize evidence in formats that are accessible to all stakeholders. Employ integrated assessments to evaluate the effectiveness, scalability, and socio-economic implications of proposed solutions. Use frameworks for systematic evidence synthesis to ensure credibility and transparency.
6. **Policy Integration and Feedback Mechanisms:** Establish iterative feedback loops between researchers, stakeholders, and policymakers. Create channels for policy interaction and feedback exchange to ensure that evidence informs decision-making at both local and regional levels. Promote bidirectional communication to align scientific findings with policy frameworks.
7. **Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer:** Provide training sessions, workshops, and knowledge transfer tools to enhance stakeholder capacity for engaging with scientific evidence. Develop targeted materials, such as policy briefs, to ensure information accessibility and applicability. Foster continuous learning among all participants.
8. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implement robust monitoring mechanisms to track the progress and impact of SPSI activities. Use participatory approaches to ensure transparency and stakeholder ownership. Regularly assess the alignment between objectives, activities, and outcomes, and adjust the process as needed.
9. **Scaling and Sustainability Planning:** Identify successful practices and innovations that can be scaled up or transferred to other contexts. Develop strategies for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the SPSI framework, including securing funding, institutional support, and stakeholder commitment.
10. **Institutionalization and Continuous Improvement:** Embed the SPSI framework into existing governance structures to ensure its integration into regional and national soil health policies. Promote institutional learning and adaptation by incorporating lessons learned from operational activities into future planning. Maintain an iterative approach to continuously improve processes and outcomes.

By following these steps, researchers can effectively establish and operationalize the SPSI within the SHLLs, creating a dynamic and collaborative framework that bridges the gap between science, policy, and societal needs while addressing soil health challenges in diverse contexts.

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